

Spreading Like Wildfire: Developing a wildfire directional vulnerability assessment for English forest managers

A dissertation submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the
degree of Master of Science (MSc) in Forestry, Bangor University

by

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Submitted: September 2025

Declarations

This dissertation is being submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Science.

This work has not previously been accepted in substance for any degree and is not being concurrently submitted in candidature for any degree.

This dissertation is the result of my own independent work/investigation except where otherwise stated.

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Ethical Statement

This research was screened under Bangor University's Research Ethics Framework. Ethics checklist completed. Full application was submitted, reference 2025-0635-3. Favourable opinion was provided on 13th February 2025.

Use of Generative AI and AI-assisted Technologies

During the preparation of this dissertation, AI (ChatGPT-4o) was used to research hazard classification and ember transmission distances. It was also used to produce prompts for R script development, help troubleshooting code in R, support work in ArcGIS Pro, and as a dictionary and thesaurus.

Presentation

This dissertation has been prepared based on the guidelines for authors for the International Journal of Wildland Fire (Appendix A).

Word Count

8,036 words (excluding abstract, figure captions, tables, and references)

Abstract

Background. Driven by a warming climate and land–use changes, fire regimes are changing, with direct and indirect environmental, social and economic impacts. The UK is increasingly vulnerable; despite policy guidance, forest managers prioritise more pressing issues. Exposure mapping was traditionally omnidirectional; the directional vulnerability assessment maps potential wildfire trajectories and encroachment on communities. **Aim.** This study tests the transferability of the directional vulnerability assessment to England’s temperate deciduous context, focusing on the New Forest, and evaluates its effectiveness as a framework for strategic wildfire risk assessment for forest managers. **Methods.** Wildfire exposure was assessed using the UKCEH Land Cover Map and a vegetation hazard classification; exposure assessments were validated against 2014–2021 burned–area data. An ArcGIS Pro trajectory delineation method and R validation script were developed for the directional vulnerability assessment; high–exposure and viable trajectory thresholds were defined. Directional vulnerability assessments were run for community and environmental values; outputs with varying segment lengths were compared and a synthesis of radial graphs analysed. **Key results.** The wildfire exposure assessment was validated for short–range exposure but not long–range. Resolution effects were small; 10 m was adopted for the community scale. The high–exposure threshold was defined at ≥ 0.8 and 61% of viable trajectories overlapped high–exposure areas for 100% of their length. The most informative segment length was 1 km. Mapping radial graphs revealed informative intersecting trajectories. **Conclusions.** Vegetation fires burn preferentially in high–exposure areas, validating the exposure assessment. The directional vulnerability assessment is customisable to the English context; a modified short–range assessment is informative at the community scale, with multiple intersecting radial graphs further supporting management decisions. **Implications.** The directional vulnerability assessment is straightforward, flexible, reproducible, and scalable with minimal data requirements. It supports forest management planning and multiple stakeholders with various responsibilities.

Keywords

directional vulnerability, England, forest management, fuel mapping, hazard classification, New Forest, risk assessment, short–range exposure, spatial data, vegetation fire, wildfire exposure

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Abbreviations

WEA	wildfire exposure assessment
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DVA	directional vulnerability assessment
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UKCEH	UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology
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Definitions

value	Any element of social, cultural, environmental or economic importance that may be adversely affected by fire, including built assets and ecological resources.
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scale	Landscape-scale assessment: national extent (England). Community-scale assessment: regional extent (Dorset-Hampshire) and local extent (built-up areas).
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fire transmission	The ability of fire to ignite nearby fuel through the mechanisms of direct flame contact, radiant heat, and ember (firebrand) spotting (Figure 1).
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Figure 1. The mechanisms of fire transmission.

The mechanisms of fire transmission – direct flame contact, radiant heat, and ember (firebrand) spotting – and the approximate distance each can extend.

exposure	The contact of an entity, asset, resource, system, or geographic area with a potential hazard (Thompson <i>et al.</i> , 2016).
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fire exposure

The extent to which the land cover type in the vicinity of a location will either contribute to or resist fire transmission to that location (Figure 2; Beverly *et al.*, 2021).

Figure 2. The exposure of cells to potential fire transmission.

Illustration comparing the exposure of cells A and B to the potential for fire transmission from nearby hazardous fuel cells (white). Red arrows represent the potential for fire transmission from hazardous fuel cells. Cell A is exposed due to the proximity of multiple hazardous fuel cells, whereas cell B is less exposed due to the non-burnable water cells surrounding it.

fire exposure
metric

A numeric rating (0–1) of the potential for fire transmission to a grid cell’s location given surrounding (hazardous) fuel composition and configuration, irrespective of weather or other fire controls (Figure 3; Beverly and Forbes, 2023).

Figure 3. Wildfire exposure rating calculation using neighbourhood analysis. Illustration showing a neighbourhood analysis calculation of a long-range wildfire exposure rating at a 500-m transmission distance for a value cell.

exposed value

Values are exposed when the potential for hazardous fuels to spread fire to them exists, and unexposed when there is no potential (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Exposed and unexposed values. Illustration showing that values are exposed when fire can potentially transmit from hazardous fuels, and unexposed when there is no transmission potential.

directional
vulnerability

The potential for wildfire transmission to encroach on an area of interest from a given direction, assessed by intersecting fire exposure levels for 360 possible 1° directional trajectories where 1° viable trajectories for a given distance interval are visualised as coloured lines in a radial graph (Figure 5; Beverly and Forbes, 2023).

Figure 5. Directional vulnerability assessment radial graph.

A radial graph illustrating the directional vulnerability of a community to wildfire encroachment. The coloured lines indicate the potential for fire transmission from surrounding areas due to a continuous trajectory of high exposure.

Red lines 0–1 km; orange lines 1–2 km; yellow lines 2–3 km.

fireexposuR

An R package developed for modelling wildfire exposure and directional vulnerability based on fire transmission potential (Forbes and Beverly, 2024a). The package was used to perform the assessments and validations in this study.

hazardous fuel

Fuel that can transmit fire over distances (Beverly *et al.*, 2021). For example, a vegetative fuel type can be hazardous at a distance of 20 m from radiant heat or short-range spotting and non-hazardous at a distance of 100 m.

non-hazardous
fuel

Fuel that cannot transmit fire over the distance under consideration (Beverly *et al.*, 2021). This can be flammable vegetation capable of producing radiant heat and fire ignition of surrounding fuel at close range, but with an ember transport range below the distance under consideration.

non-burnable

Land cover that cannot support combustion, e.g. water, barren ground, rock (Beverly *et al.*, 2021).

1. Introduction

1.1 Global Context

Wildfire activity is changing in complex ways worldwide, with contrasting trends emerging (Sayedi *et al.*, 2024). Global burned area declined by about 22% and total fire counts decreased by 10% between 2005 and 2020 (Tang *et al.*, 2024). However, at regional scales, fire intensity, size, severity, and season length have increased (Wasserman and Mueller, 2023). Consequently, there is growing concern about direct and indirect social, environmental and economic impacts, such as the 33 deaths and 3,000 houses destroyed by the Australian Black Summer fires (Filkov *et al.*, 2020) and the estimated 1.53 million deaths annually between 2000 and 2019 due to air pollution from landscape fires (Xu *et al.*, 2024).

The drivers of these altered fire regimes vary regionally yet can be broadly summarised as: colonial fire suppression, characterised by the criminalisation and violent suppression of Indigenous burning practices (Norgaard, 2014); land use change, such as the rapid expansion of the WUI¹ (Chen *et al.*, 2024); vegetation change (Sparks *et al.*, 2024); and climate change (Jones *et al.*, 2022). These factors are frequently interrelated, which can produce contrasting outcomes. For example, while fire is a natural part of the boreal forest ecosystem in Canada, historic fire suppression, the expansion of the WUI, and climate change have resulted in significant changes to the fire regime, yet research shows that human-caused fires declined between 1980 and 2015 (Hanes *et al.*, 2019; Whitman *et al.*, 2022).

1.2 British Context

In the UK², a wildfire is any uncontrolled vegetation fire that meets one or more criteria regarding its size or the resources required to suppress it (Scottish Government, 2013). The country is becoming increasingly vulnerable to wildfire due to climate change and ongoing demographic and settlement changes (HM Government, 2022; Perry *et al.*, 2022), and across the south and east, models predict that the average number of wildfire danger days will increase 3–4 times by the 2080s (Figure 6; Arnell *et al.*, 2021a).

¹ Wildland–urban interface – in the British context, referred to as the rural–urban interface due to the absence of wildlands (McMorrow *et al.*, 2021).

² To clarify, this study refers to Great Britain/GB/British (i.e. England, Scotland and Wales) in terms of the geographical entity, and ‘the UK’ when referring to the political entity of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland.

Figure 6. Comparison of very high fire danger days over the UK. Percentage of summer days with very high fire danger (Fire Weather Index > 17.35) over the UK, comparing (a) historical data with future climate modelling at (b) 2 °C and (c) 4 °C global warming. Reproduced from Perry *et al.* (2022) under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence.

Wildfires have severe social, environmental and economic impacts (Flage *et al.*, 2014): the 2011 Swinley Forest fire had a total social cost of over £1 million (Wrack, 2023) and the recent wildfires in the Scottish Highlands caused catastrophic damage to wildlife (McKenzie and Davies, 2025). However, they remain an under-recognised hazard (Arnell *et al.*, 2021b) despite being formally acknowledged as a national risk in 2013 (Gazzard *et al.*, 2016).

The UK Climate Change Risk Assessment identifies increased temperatures, along with extreme events such as drought and wildfire, as among the greatest threats to the viability of habitats and species (HM Government, 2022), and the UK Forestry Standard advises managers to assess potential risks from hazards such as wind, fire, higher temperatures, drought, waterlogging, and pest or disease outbreaks (Forest Research, 2023). Despite these acknowledgements, the UK lacks a specific national wildfire strategy, and responsibility for wildfire management is fragmented across multiple government departments (Thorp, 2021). Severe wildfires are infrequent, with return intervals longer than a government’s term in office and the emergency planning timeframe of five years. As a result, responses to severe wildfires have so far been *ad hoc*, and have evolved at the local level. While

national-level guidance exists on wildfire management and forest management planning (Forestry Commission, 2014), there is no legislation enforcing these guidelines, and local management structures and policy implementation remain inconsistent (Gazzard *et al.*, 2016; Moffat and Gazzard, 2019).

1.3 Literature Review

1.3.1 Fire in Temperate Deciduous Ecosystems and Britain

The temperate deciduous forest biome occurs mainly in eastern North America, northern and central Europe, and East Asia (Loidi and Marcenò, 2022). Fire regimes are characterised by infrequent, patchy, short-range fires shaped by human activity, with flammability largely determined by leaf-litter traits and site moisture (Kreye *et al.*, 2023). Human fire exclusion has driven succession from fire-tolerant, flammable species such as oaks to shade-tolerant, mesophytic species such as beeches, creating a feedback loop that suppresses fire and promotes mesophication, well documented in eastern North American oak-pine forests (Alexander *et al.*, 2021).

Fire was a natural part of the British landscape from the Late Jurassic period (161–145 million yr BP³) until the Neolithic agricultural revolution (4,000 yr BP) (Simmons and Innes, 1987; Matthewman *et al.*, 2012), and evidence suggests that the use of fire by Late Palaeolithic, Mesolithic and Neolithic humans to support their hunting and gathering activities was very common (Groves *et al.*, 2012). As humans transitioned into agricultural and pastoral farming systems, fire use shifted to land clearance, with controlled burning continuing as a management tool on grasslands and heathlands (Swindles *et al.*, 2021) but overall, fire use in land management declined (Ryan and Blackford, 2010) and the agricultural burning of crop residues is now prohibited (*The Crop Residues (Burning) Regulations 1993*). Prescribed burning has remained a land management tool in upland heaths, moors and peatlands, as well as in the New Forest's lowland heaths, but is highly controversial (Douglas *et al.*, 2016).

Evidence indicates that vegetation phenology is a key driver of fire occurrence in the UK; fires in semi-natural grasslands and dwarf-shrub heaths peak in early spring when vegetation is still dormant, with a marked decline during the high-greenness phase despite high fire-weather indices, though this

³ Dates in the reviewed research papers are estimated from carbon dating, the “present” being 1950, and are given in various formats: 12,000 cal b.p.; 12,000 ¹⁴C yr BP; 12,000 b.c., or similar. “yr BP” is used here for simplicity, and the time periods are approximate.

resistance weakens during severe droughts (Nikonovas *et al.*, 2024). In woodland dynamics, natural fire has played a negligible role (Simmons *et al.*, 2022), making fire-driven successional feedback less relevant, highlighting a key difference from other temperate deciduous ecosystems.

1.3.2 Wildfire Modelling and Risk Assessment

Remote sensing, GIS and computer modelling developed in the Americas have significantly contributed to the emergence of powerful tools such as FlamMap (potential fire behaviour characteristics; Finney, 2006), the Canadian Forest Fire Danger Rating System (incorporating metrics such as a Fire Weather Index and Drought Code; Stocks *et al.*, 1989) and Prometheus (fire risk assessment; Tymstra *et al.*, 2010). These tools were developed to support the paradigm of suppression, focusing on fire behaviour prediction in order to inform real-time emergency response and preparedness.

Recognition that fire regimes are significantly changing has shifted attention from deterministic models to proactive mitigation over larger areas and longer decision horizons. Tools such as the Fire Simulation System (FSim) support this by simulating thousands of stochastic ignitions to model burn probability and fire intensity across landscapes (Finney *et al.*, 2011). Landscape-scale risk assessment now relies on such burn-probability modelling to identify areas of recurrent exposure. However, simulated burn probability maps are now found to be poorly aligned with subsequent observed wildfires (e.g. Fort McMurray; Beverly *et al.*, 2021). Meanwhile, statistical approaches, more common in Europe, model wildfire occurrence as a function of historical fire data, environmental and socio-economic variables, enabling rapid scenario testing without the computational demands of full fire-spread simulations (Oliveira *et al.*, 2021).

In Britain, these tools have been investigated (Krivtsov and Legg, 2011; de Jong *et al.*, 2016) and work done to produce UK-specific ones: the MOFSI⁴ and the UKFDRS.⁵ However, research is sparse and tends to focus on moorland rather than forest fires (Davies and Legg, 2008). The UKFDRS is at a formative stage, with research results recently published. These focus on leaf-litter flammability and fuel moisture dynamics (e.g. Ivison *et al.*, 2024; Crawford *et al.*, 2025), and although the system aspires to encompass multiple fuel classes, current outputs cover surface fuel layers but not tree canopy or woody biomass, indicating that full forest-fire modelling capability is not yet achieved.

⁴ Met Office Fire Severity Index

⁵ UK Fire Danger Rating System

1.3.3 Wildfire Exposure and Directional Vulnerability

In wildfire research, exposure is defined in various ways; in this study, it is stated in the Definitions section, as used by Beverly *et al.* (2021). Wildfire exposure refers to the potential for fire to spread to any given location from the surrounding area, based on its contagious nature and the configuration of nearby fuels. It is quantified using a neighbourhood analysis to produce a numeric rating that reflects fuel composition and arrangement, irrespective of weather or other dynamic factors (Beverly *et al.*, 2021), and bridges real-time suppression operations and longer-term risk assessment. Validation of the exposure metric against observed fire perimeters has shown that burned areas appear preferentially in areas of high exposure (Schmidt *et al.*, 2024; Khan *et al.*, 2025a) and a key strength of this approach is its computational efficiency and minimal data requirements.

While the prediction of dynamic factors is absolutely crucial to emergency responders, strategic mitigation planning can be done with simplified fire exposure models based solely on fuel distribution (Karimi *et al.*, 2024; Kim *et al.*, 2024; Schmidt *et al.*, 2024), with research suggesting that such models can be highly effective at the local scale (e.g. Swan Hills; Beverly *et al.*, 2010), particularly when compared with other, more complex methods such as burn probability mapping (Beverly and McLoughlin, 2019).

However, as fire does not spread evenly from its source of ignition, omnidirectional risk assessments can be limiting, particularly at the local scale. Research has sought to refine the wildfire exposure assessment (WEA) by examining fire spread trajectories, enabling real-time suppression and evacuation activities (Campbell *et al.*, 2019), informing strategic fuel treatment planning within the broader context of reducing community vulnerabilities (Sá *et al.*, 2022), and supporting long-term policy and resource allocation decisions (Syphard *et al.*, 2018).

In simplified form, the directional nature of fire is influenced by wind (an exogenous and dynamic factor), topography, and fuel characteristics/distribution (both endogenous and static factors). While the wind speed and slope affect the rate of spread (Hayajneh and Naser, 2025), the fuel load affects fire intensity and the continuity of the trajectory (Haas *et al.*, 2024), with wind direction, landscape morphology and aspect also contributing (Wang *et al.*, 2024). In reality, the mix of factors is highly complex and much work has been done in developing data-driven computer models (Altamimi *et al.*, 2022; Yoo *et al.*, 2024). Effort has also been made to decouple the dynamic and static factors, acknowledging that dynamic factors can only be predicted in the short term, while static factors can be predicted in the medium to long term (Beverly and Forbes, 2023).

Directional models, such as the directional vulnerability assessment (DVA), fill a methodological and operational gap by enabling spatially explicit mitigation planning in contexts where real-time data are unavailable or uncertain. When combined with wind direction forecasts, they can also support short-horizon emergency response (Kim *et al.*, 2024), complementing dynamic forecasting used in suppression planning.

1.4 Research Gap and Justification

Wildfire research is understandably focused in regions with intense wildfire activity (e.g. North America, Mediterranean Europe), which predisposes less fire-prone regions to research gaps. Wildfire research in the UK has largely been limited to fire in upland vegetation (e.g. Baker *et al.*, 2025), while research into forest fires or wildfire exposure at either landscape or community scales has yet to be pursued. Recently developed methods for fire trajectory mapping have also not been applied in Britain, with applications to date limited to boreal ecosystems in Canada (Kim *et al.*, 2024; Kuiper and Beverly, 2025). It has been acknowledged that assessments could be applied in other geographical areas with adjustments to account for different fire regime characteristics (Beverly *et al.*, 2010), and also provide a more detailed assessment of viable fire trajectories adjacent to built-up areas (Beverly and Forbes, 2023).

With fewer than 3% of wildfires occurring in forests (McMorrow *et al.*, 2015), forest managers prioritise other, more pressing threats (Tew *et al.*, 2024) and generally do not plan to increase wildfire resilience, despite policy guidance (Forestry Commission, 2017; Gazzard, 2022). Research in Canada suggests that insurance premiums are a more effective strategy for mitigating wildfire risk to timber supplies (Rodriguez-Baca *et al.*, 2016), but this does not address social and environmental values. The wildfire exposure metric can identify when such values lie in an area of high wildfire exposure without needing to predict ignitions or fire weather.

1.5 Research Aims and Questions

This study aims to provide a practical tool that aids forest managers with decision making, improves wildfire resilience, and reduces the environmental, social and economic impacts of wildfires in England. It tests the applicability of the DVA to the temperate deciduous context of England, using deductive reasoning by testing hypotheses about wildfire exposure, fire trajectory overlap and parameter sensitivity, and inductive reasoning to assess its applicability to other ecosystems. The study also evaluates whether the DVA is informative for decision making.

The study tested the following null hypotheses:

1. **Wildfire exposure.** Fires do not occur preferentially in high–exposure areas.
2. **Fire trajectories.** Fire trajectories do not intersect high–exposure areas for most of their length.
3. **Parameters.** Land–cover resolution, seasonal hazard classification, fire transmission distances and DVA segment length have no significant effect on assessment results, and therefore do not require customisation for the English context.

To achieve this, the study addresses three groups of research questions (Table 1), covering WEA, seasonal hazard classification, and the DVA itself. Q1c tests whether fires occur preferentially in high–exposure areas; Q3a tests whether trajectories intersect high–exposure areas; and the remaining questions test whether results are sensitive to resolution, seasonal hazard classification, transmission distance and segment length.

Table 1. Research questions and baseline parameters.

Research questions and associated parameters from published research, which provide the baseline for the unmodified DVA used to test the null hypothesis.

Research Question		Published Research	References (abbreviated to first author for clarity)
1. Wildfire Exposure Assessment (WEA)	Q1a. What is the most suitable land cover resolution for landscape–scale WEAs?	100 m	Beverly (2021, 2023) Forbes (2024b) Khan (2025b)
		30 m	Forbes (2024b) Schmidt (2024) Kuiper (2025)
	Q1b. What is the most suitable land cover resolution for community–scale WEAs?	30 m	Forbes (2024b) Karimi (2024)
		10 m	Forbes (2024b)
		5 m	Beverly (2010) Khan (2025a)
		3 m	Forbes (2024b)
	Q1c. What threshold of fire exposure defines high–exposure areas?	60%	Beverly (2021, 2023) Kim (2024) Schmidt (2024) Khan (2025a, b) Kuiper (2025)

		45%: individual telecommunications towers	Kuiper (2025)
		30%: in the built environment	Beverly (2010) Forbes (2024b)
2. Seasonal Hazard Classification	Q2a. What are the hazard classifications for spring and summer?	Canadian Fire Behaviour Prediction System / Alberta Wildfire	Beverly (2010, 2021, 2023) Forbes (2024b) Karimi (2024) Kim (2024) Kuiper (2025)
		Alaska Wildland Fire Coordinating Group (2018) Fuel Model Guide	Schmidt (2024)
		peer-reviewed literature and local expert panel	Khan (2025a, b)
	Q2b. Which seasonal hazard classification is most appropriate for use in WEAs?	Combined: fuel counts as hazardous if it is hazardous in any season (not possible to partition spring / summer at coarser resolutions).	Beverly (2010, 2021, 2023) Forbes (2024b)
		Spring: more hazardous because it includes grass and aspen (only possible to partition the classification for finer resolution assessments due to their shorter transmission distances).	Beverly (2021)
	3. Directional Vulnerability Assessment (DVA)	Q3a. What percentage of a given fire trajectory overlaps high exposure?	80%
Q3b. What fire transmission distances are appropriate?		long-range embers 500 m short-range embers 100 m radiant heat 30 m	Beverly (2010, 2021, 2023) Forbes (2024b) Karimi (2024) Kim (2024) Schmidt (2024) Khan (2025a, b) Kuiper (2025)
Q3c. What is the optimal DVA segment length?		5 km	Beverly (2023) Kim (2024) Kuiper (2025)

2. Methods

2.1 Study Area

The WEA focuses on the English temperate deciduous ecosystem only, as preliminary work revealed different validation results for Scotland compared with Britain as a whole (Appendix B). On average, 30,000 wildfire incidents occurred annually in England between 2009 and 2021 (Forestry Commission, 2023), providing mapped burned areas sufficient in extent to validate the assessments. Preliminary analysis also indicated that radiant heat assessments were not useful because uniformly high exposure values left little distinction between areas. The study therefore focuses on long- and short-range ember exposure to provide a more targeted analysis that better supports longer-term management decisions.

The DVA further focuses on two counties, Dorset and Hampshire (Figure 7), located in the south of England where wildfire risk is higher (Figure 6). Burned area perimeters for Dorset were provided to the author (pers. comm. Elliott, 2025) and the New Forest National Park provided a mix of community and environmental values that could be assessed holistically.

The study area is characterised by chalk downlands, heathlands, lowland deciduous woodlands, river valleys, and a complex coastline. Land cover includes significant areas of arable farmland, pasture, and ancient woodland, with extensive heathland in the New Forest and Dorset Heaths (Natural England, 2025). These lowland heaths are of high conservation value but are also fire-prone due to their dry, acidic soils and dominance of heather and gorse. Wildfires occur regularly during dry periods, with ignition sources often linked to human activity, causing authorities such as Forestry England to issue warnings (Silver, 2025). Population density varies, with urban concentrations along the coast, while much of the inland rural landscape remains sparsely populated. Within Hampshire, the New Forest is 29,000 ha and designated a Special Area of Conservation, with extensive heath, scrub and broadleaved deciduous woodland (JNCC, 2025).

Figure 7. Map of study area within European context.

Location of the study area on the south coast of England, UK. The inset map (top) shows the position of the United Kingdom and Republic of Ireland within Europe.

For the community–scale analysis a sample of communities were selected. This process delineated three communities for analysis in Dorset, to provide a baseline comparison, and 13 within the New Forest. A conifer plantation and a conservation area were selected as environmental values due to their proximity to each other and a community (Figure 8).

Sources: IGN, Esri UK, Esri, HERE, Garmin, INCREMENT P, USGS, METI/NASA, NGA, Forest Research, Historic England, Office for National Statistics licensed under the Open Government Licence v.3.0, contains OS data © Crown copyright and database right 2025.

Figure 8. Map of study area with New Forest detail.

Upper map: Dorset and Hampshire showing 16 community and two environmental values assessed in this study; the red box indicates the extent of the lower map. Lower map: 14 community polygons created from continuous built–up areas, and two environmental values.

2.2 Workflow

The workflow (Table 2) summarises the steps and the data required for each. The outputs from Steps 1, 2 and 4 provided inputs to others.

Table 2. Overview of workflow.

An overview of the five steps in the workflow with corresponding inputs and outputs.

Workflow Step	Inputs	Outputs
1. WEA	land cover raster hazard classification non-burnable classification R script 3	exposure raster
2. WEA validation	burned area polygons exposure raster R script 4	exposure validation result high exposure threshold
3. WEA validation statistical analyses	exposure validation result R script 5	chi-squared test p -value
	exposure raster burned area polygons R script 6	Wilcoxon rank sum test p -value
4. DVA validation	exposure raster spine fire trajectories R script 7 high exposure threshold	DVA validation viable trajectory threshold
5. DVA	exposure raster value polygon R script 10 viable trajectory threshold	DVA radial graphs

2.3 Data Sources

2.3.1 Third-party data

Land cover data, burned area data and shapefiles were accessed from open online sources (Table 3).

Table 3. Description of study datasets.

Purpose	Name	Year	Source of Download	Res.	Format	Reference
Land cover raster	Land Cover Map GB	2023	EDINA DigiMap	10m	.tif classified pixels	(Morton <i>et al.</i> , 2024a)
	Land Cover Map GB	2023	EDINA DigiMap	25m	.tif rasterised land parcels	(Morton <i>et al.</i> , 2024b)
Polygon	Built-Up Areas Boundaries GB	2022	Open Geography Portal		.shp	(Office for National Statistics, 2022a)
	Conservation Areas	2022	Historic England Open Data Hub		.shp	(Historic England, 2022)
	Counties and Unitary Authorities UK	2023	Open Geography Portal		.shp	(Office for National Statistics, 2024)
	National Forest Inventory	2023	Forestry Commission Open Data		.shp	(Forest Research, 2024)
	National Parks Boundaries GB	2020	Open Geography Portal		.shp	(Office for National Statistics, 2022b)
Burned area data	Updated 30 m Resolution Global Annual Burned Area Map (GABAM) (2014–2021)	2024	Zenodo	30m	.tif	Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	Dorset burn perimeters (2002–2025)	2025	personal communication		.shp	Elliott (2025)

Step 1 required recent, reliable land cover data for GB at different resolutions that could be accessed from an open source in ready-to-use formats compatible with ArcGIS Pro. Several datasets were considered for this analysis: MODIS⁶ data offered frequent temporal coverage but its spatial resolution (250–500 m) was too coarse for the scale of analysis required while CLC⁷ data was only available for the year 2018 and earlier.

⁶ Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration

⁷ CORINE (Coordination of Information on the Environment) Land Cover from the European Environment Agency

The UKCEH Land Cover Map 2023 was chosen because it is reliable and contains official UK land cover data at the multiple resolutions required, from recent years, and was easily accessible from EDINA's Digimap. It is also available for the year 1990 onwards should further research into change over time be investigated. The land cover classes are based on the 21 categories derived from Biodiversity Action Plan Broad Habitats and were suitable for this study (Appendix C).

The dataset has an accuracy of 83% based on 33,107 validation points and consists of 10 m pixel data, classified land parcels, 25 m rasterised parcels, and a 1 km summary raster (UKCEH, 2020). Preliminary analysis identified persistent processing errors when utilising the 25 m raster, likely due to it being derived from the land parcel vector, which in turn was derived from the 10 m raster. To provide consistency of base data across all resolutions, the 10 m raster was resampled to create the other resolution rasters for use in this study.

Shapefiles were required to define national- and county-scale clipping polygons for the land cover rasters (Step 1), and to delineate the local-scale values assessed (Step 5). Reliable datasets were accessed from open government data portals (Table 3).

Several alternative datasets documenting burned areas were considered for Steps 2–4. The GABAM dataset was chosen due to its finer resolution (30 m, compared with 250 m and 1 km alternatives), eight-year coverage (2014–2021), consistent and reproducible Google Earth Engine-based automated workflow across all regions and years, rigorous validation, and ease of access. For each year, only the five tiles covering Britain were accessed.

Burn perimeter shapefiles, created with GPS, were generously shared with the author (Elliott, 2025). These data were omitted from the main workflow because they are not publicly available, but provide a valuable comparison against the GABAM dataset and were instrumental in developing the method used to automate fire trajectory production for DVA validation (Step 4).

2.3.2 Data derived from original research

Other data required for this study were generated from original research.

a) Seasonal hazard classifications

A spring and a summer hazard classification were required for the WEA (Step 1). In Canada, hazard is defined nationally through the Fire Behaviour Prediction System. The UK has no equivalent framework, so a bespoke classification was compiled from literature and consultation with experts (Khan *et al.*, 2025a, b).

Literature review of peer-reviewed papers, wildfire reports and other documents produced limited results, with resources such as FireInSite focusing on fire behaviour rather than hazard characterisation. In response, AI-assisted deep research was pursued. This involved a structured synthesis of academic and grey literature sources, combining wildfire incident data, official UK wildfire guidance, and fire danger rating system documentation to generate a classification of British vegetation fuel hazard by season and ignition. Although 17 key sources were identified, full retrieval of every document was not possible (Appendix D).

An online questionnaire to survey expert opinions was hosted by a secure survey platform and conducted in accordance with the approved ethics protocol at Bangor University. British fire fighters with experience responding to vegetation fires were invited to complete the survey anonymously with a respondent link distributed via LinkedIn, the Northumberland Wildfire Group, and the England and Wales Wildfire Forum (Appendix E).

Due to the requirement to use a binary classification, in instances where experts were not unanimous or wholly consistent with the literature, the modal response was used to determine each class.

b) Non-burnable classification

A non-burnable land cover classification is required for the WEA (Step 1) because it is not meaningful to calculate wildfire exposure for a cell that cannot support combustion; those cells are discarded prior to further analysis (Beverly *et al.*, 2021). For precision, burned area data for GB (2014–2021) were analysed to identify UKCEH land cover categories that contributed a minimal proportion of total burned area. Although low percentages may result from small spatial extent, the results were consistent with expectations for non-burnable categories such as water and rock, and the threshold was set at < 0.1% (Appendix F).

2.4 Software

Software applications used are listed in Table 4. Version updates introduced no material difference to functionality, and results were unaffected.

Table 4. Software applications.

Software applications, associated versions, and description of usage during the study.

Tool	Software (version)	Use
Document Preparation	Microsoft Word (v 2505)	Writing and formatting
	Microsoft Excel (v 2505)	Data checks and organisation
	Zotero (v 6.0.36)	Reference management
Programming and Analysis	R (v 4.5.0)	WEA, statistical tests and DVA
	R Studio (v 2025.05.0)	Script development and workflow automation
	R package: fireexposuR (1.1.0)	WEA and DVA modelling
	R package: terra (1.8.42)	Raster data handling and processing
	R package: glue (1.8.0)	Creating R scripts from templates
	R package: readr (2.1.5)	For use with glue()
	R package: dplyr (1.1.4)	Validation of DVA
	R package: ggplot2 (3.5.2)	Creating histograms
GIS	ArcGIS Pro (v 3.5.2)	Spatial data preparation, wildfire exposure mapping, directional vulnerability mapping, production of map figures
AI Assistance	ChatGPT-4o	Hazard classification and ember transmission distances research; R script prompts and troubleshooting code; dictionary and thesaurus

2.5 Data Preparation

The data preparation flowcharts are summarised in Figures 9–11, with details in Appendix G.

Figure 9. Flowchart for polygon preparation.

Flowchart for preparing the national, county and value polygons for Steps 1 and 5.

Figure 10. Flowchart for land cover raster preparation.

Flowchart for preparing the GB land cover raster for Step 1.

Figure 11. Flowchart for burned area raster preparation.

Flowchart for preparing the GB burned area data for Steps 2–4.

2.6 Viable Fire Trajectories

The DVA evaluates the potential exposure of a location to wildfire encroaching along any of 360 possible 1° directional trajectories and is based on the contagious nature of fire across a landscape. To validate the metric, observed fire trajectories are compared to an exposure assessment to ascertain the extent to which fire trajectories intersect high exposure areas (Step 4). Fire trajectories are not documented in historical records and so must be inferred from the typical elliptical shape of fire spread, assuming ignition occurs near the narrow end and fire advances along the long axis (Figure 12; Van Wagner, 1969; Albini, 1976).

Figure 12. Models of fire shape and trajectory formation.

(a) Diagram showing the intersection of two blue lines where fire is presumed to start (after Albini, 1976).

(b) Diagram of a simple fire growth model (after Van Wagner, 1969). The head of the fire burns a fan-shaped area (orange V) that widens as it advances. Red arrow represents direction of fire trajectory.

Previous research has delineated viable fire trajectories within historical fire polygons manually (Beverly and Forbes 2023). Two methods were investigated in ArcGIS Pro to see whether viable fire trajectories could be created automatically (Appendix H).

2.7 R Script Preparation

Ten R scripts were required for the workflow (Table 5 and Appendix I). Scripts 1 and 8 were based on the scripts provided by developers of the WEA and DVA (Beverly and Forbes, 2024). Scripts 2, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 9 were custom-developed for this study using prompts and trouble-shooting support from ChatGPT.

Table 5. List of R scripts required to complete the workflow.

R Script number	Purpose	Workflow Step
1	WEA template	
2	mail merge instructions v1	
3	WEA x23 (output of script 1)	1
4	WEA validation	2
5	chi-squared test	3
6	Wilcoxon rank sum test	3
7	DVA validation	4
8	DVA template	
9	mail merge instructions v2	
10	DVA x66 (output of script 8)	5

Multiple scripts were needed to run the WEAs and DVAs using different parameters. To ensure accuracy between scripts, a template and a data table were written, then merged to produce identical scripts, save for the parameters (Appendix J).

2.8 WEA and Validation

Step 1 produced exposure rasters necessary for addressing the research questions and validating the assessment by comparing the distribution of overlap between exposure classes and the observed burned areas. Using the 30-m resolution exposure raster, each cell was classified by its exposure class (at 0.2 intervals) and counted to determine the expected totals. Then it was overlaid with the burned area map and the number of burned cells for each exposure class counted to determine the observed totals. A surplus of observed over expected burned area in the high exposure classes defined the high exposure threshold required for Step 4. An absence of a surplus in high exposure classes indicated that the assessment was not validated. Step 3 involved a statistical analysis of the observed versus expected overlap using chi-squared and Wilcoxon rank sum tests following Beverly *et al.* (2021).

2.9 DVA and Validation

Validation of the DVA (Step 4) required identification of fire trajectories within the burned area perimeters. Two automated methods were tested in ArcGIS Pro, flowlines and spines, with the latter being selected for validation (Appendix H). The trajectories were overlaid on a binary high-exposure

layer, and the length of each trajectory intersecting high–exposure areas was measured. This produced the viable trajectory threshold required for Step 5.

The DVA was initially run on the chosen values using the 5–km segment length as per the default value in fireexposuR and the published literature. Based upon the sparse results, shorter segment lengths of 3 km and 1 km were then assessed.

3. Key Results

3.1 Research Question 1 – Wildfire Exposure Assessment

Q1a. What is the most suitable land cover resolution for landscape–scale WEAs?

At the landscape scale, WEA for long–range exposure using 10 m resolution data was prohibited due to insufficient processing power. Visual comparison between WEA maps generated with coarser resolutions showed no discernible difference (Figure 13), and subtracting one exposure raster from another confirmed that cell–level differences were minimal (± 0.19) (Figure 14). Comparison of the 30 m and 100 m binary exposure rasters set at ≥ 0.8 revealed that only 0.11% of cells crossed the threshold, indicating 30 m is sufficient for detail and 100 m for processing efficiency.⁸

Figure 13. Maps of long–range wildfire exposure in England.

Maps of long–range wildfire exposure in England (summer hazard classification) comparing input land cover data resolutions: (a) 30 m, (b) 50 m, and (c) 100 m.

⁸ Long–range exposure was not validated at this transmission distance (Research Question 3b).

Figure 14. Maps of cell-level differences between long-range wildfire exposure maps in England. Maps of cell-level differences in England (summer hazard classification) produced by subtracting long-range wildfire exposure maps (Figure 13) in ArcGIS Pro, showing cell-level variation: (a) 30 m raster minus 50 m raster results ranged from -0.06 to $+0.06$, (b) 30 m raster minus 100 m raster results ranged from -0.17 to $+0.19$.

The WEA for short-range exposure using 10 m resolution data was prohibited due to insufficient processing power; the 50 m and 100 m data are too coarse for estimating short-range exposure (Appendix G.2, point 5); the 30 m data were successfully applied (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Map of short-range wildfire exposure in England. Map of short-range wildfire exposure in England (summer hazard classification) using 30 m resolution data.

Q1b. What is the most suitable land cover resolution for community-scale WEAs?

Visual comparison between long-range WEA maps generated with different input data resolutions showed no discernible difference (Figure 16), and the cell-level differences were minimal (± 0.21)

(Figure 17). Comparison of the 10 m and 100 m binary exposure rasters set at ≥ 0.8 revealed that only 0.11% of cells crossed the threshold, indicating 10 m is sufficient with respect to detail and processing efficiency, and has the added benefit of maintaining the original resolution.⁹

Figure 16. Maps of long-range wildfire exposure in Dorset-Hampshire.

Maps of long-range wildfire exposure in Dorset-Hampshire (summer hazard classification) comparing input land cover data resolutions: (a) 10 m, (b) 30 m, (c) 50 m, and (d) 100 m.

⁹ Long-range exposure was not validated at this transmission distance (Research Question 3b).

Figure 17. Maps of cell-level differences between long-range wildfire exposure maps in Dorset-Hampshire. Maps of cell-level differences in Dorset-Hampshire (summer hazard classification) produced by subtracting long-range wildfire exposure maps (Figure 16) in ArcGIS Pro, showing cell-level variation: (a) 10 m raster minus 30 m raster results ranged from -0.06 to $+0.06$, (b) 10 m raster minus 50 m raster results ranged from -0.08 to $+0.09$, (c) 10 m raster minus 100 m raster results ranged from -0.2 to $+0.2$.

For short-range exposure, 50 m and 100 m data are too coarse (Appendix G.2, point 5). The 10 m and 30 m data were successfully applied (Figure 18), and the cell-level differences were minimal (± 0.31) (Figure 19). Comparison of the 10 m and 30 m binary exposure rasters set at ≥ 0.8 revealed that only 2.3% of cells crossed the threshold, indicating 10 m data are sufficient for both detail and processing efficiency, with the additional benefit of being the original resolution.

Figure 18. Maps of short-range wildfire exposure in Dorset-Hampshire.

Maps of short-range wildfire exposure in Dorset-Hampshire (summer hazard classification) comparing input land cover data resolutions: (a) 10 m and (b) 30 m.

Figure 19. Map of cell-level differences between short-range wildfire exposure maps in Dorset-Hampshire. Map of cell-level differences in Dorset-Hampshire (summer hazard classification) produced by subtracting short-range wildfire exposure maps (Figure 18) in ArcGIS Pro, showing cell-level variation of 10 m raster minus 30 m raster results ranged from -0.26 to $+0.31$.

Q1c. *What threshold of fire exposure defines high-exposure areas?*

The comparison between expected and observed values for long-range exposure revealed a surplus of burned cells in the Nil exposure class (Figure 20a), indicating that the metric's high-exposure areas did not correspond with fire occurrence. Therefore, the long-range WEA for a 500 m transmission distance was not validated for England. Further experimentation with 300 m and 200 m transmission distances produced similar results (Appendix K).

For short-range exposure, a surplus of burned areas was observed in the 0.8–1 exposure class (Figure 20b), indicating that fires burned preferentially in high exposure areas. This validated the short-range

WEA at a 100 m transmission distance for England and defined high exposure at 80% for input to the DVA validation (Step 4).

(a) long-range exposure (500 m)

(b) short-range exposure (100 m)

Figure 20. Comparison between expected and observed burned area across exposure class for long- and short-range exposure.

Comparison between expected (dashed bar) and observed (solid bar) burned area across exposure class (summer hazard classification) using a 0.5% sample (left) and total (right): (a) long-range exposure (500 m) and (b) short-range exposure (100 m).

These results were confirmed with a chi-squared test and Wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction, which both returned significant p -values of < 0.001 (Appendix L).

3.2 Research Question 2 – Seasonal Hazard Classification

Q2a. What are the hazard classifications for spring and summer?

As expected, some vegetative fuels were found to be hazardous at short-range and non-hazardous at long-range, and/or hazardous in summer but not in spring. Conservatively, fuels were only defined as non-hazardous if deemed to be consistently not hazardous at a given transmission distance for the whole season. A synthesis of the research (Table 6) revealed differences in hazardous levels between spring and summer, for example, arable at short-range and heather at long-range. Differences were also identified between long- and short-range exposure, for example, heather grassland in spring and fen in summer.

Table 6. Binary hazard classification.

Binary hazard classification: 1 = hazardous; 0 = non-hazardous. Fuels defined as non-hazardous if deemed to be consistently not hazardous at a given transmission distance for the whole season.

Land Cover Class	Season and Exposure Range			
	spring		summer	
	short (100 m)	long (500 m)	short (100 m)	long (500 m)
1 Deciduous woodland	0	0	0	0
2 Coniferous woodland	1	1	1	1
3 Arable	0	0	1	0
4 Improve grassland	0	0	0	0
5 Neutral grassland	0	0	1	0
6 Calcareous grassland	0	0	0	0
7 Acid grassland	1	0	1	0
8 Fen	0	0	1	0
9 Heather	1	0	1	1
10 Heather grassland	1	0	1	1
11 Bog	0	0	0	0

Q2b. Which seasonal hazard classification is most appropriate for use in WEAs?

It is possible to partition the fuel hazard classification by season for both transmission distances when finer resolution land cover data are used (Figure 21; Beverly *et al.*, 2021). Summer was selected as the preferred classification and is considered a conservative choice given that all hazardous fuel classes are hazardous during the summer season, but not always in spring, for example, arable. Although this contrasts with evidence of higher spring fire occurrence (Nikonovas *et al.*, 2024), the classification defines the capacity of vegetation to ignite fuel at a distance via ember transport rather than the vegetation's intrinsic flammability following its ignition. Nonetheless, it is also accurate to conclude that the hazard classification is combined, i.e. fuel counts as hazardous if it is hazardous in any season (Beverly *et al.*, 2010).

(a) long-range exposure using 30 m resolution data

(b) long-range exposure using 10 m resolution data

(c) short-range exposure using 10 m resolution data

Figure 21. Comparison of spring and summer wildfire exposure assessment maps.

Comparison of spring (left) and summer (right) wildfire exposure assessment maps: (a) long-range exposure map of England using 30 m resolution data, (b) long-range exposure map of Dorset-Hampshire using 10 m resolution data, and (c) short-range exposure map of Dorset-Hampshire using 10 m resolution data.

3.3 Research Question 3 – Directional Vulnerability Assessment

Q3a. What percentage of a given fire trajectory overlaps high exposure?

The DVA validation (Step 4) was completed using the spine fire trajectories. The majority (61%) of viable fire trajectories exhibited 100% intersection with high-exposure areas. The summary graph shows a slightly higher percentage (65%) of viable fire trajectories with 95–100% of their length intersecting high exposure areas (Figure 22). For the purposes of this study, 100% overlap was selected as a reasonable threshold for viability for input to the DVAs (Step 5).

Figure 22. Frequency of fire trajectories by percentage of trajectory length intersection with high exposure areas.

Q3b. What fire transmission distances are appropriate?

The 500 m, 300 m and 200 m transmission distances for long-range exposure are not appropriate because they were not validated (see Q1c above). The 100 m transmission distance for short-range exposure was validated (Q1c) and used for the DVAs (Steps 4 and 5).

Q3c. What is the optimal DVA segment length?

Sixteen communities (Figure 8) were assessed using three different segment lengths (Step 5). Two communities (Everton; Milford on Sea and Keyhaven) had no viable fire trajectories at any segment length, and one (Tiptoe *et al.*) had none at 5 km or 3 km, and a very sparse result at 1 km; these were therefore removed from further analysis.

For the 5–km segment length, only two DVAs identified viable fire trajectories (Figure 23), and for the 3–km segment length, 10 DVAs identified viable fire trajectories (Figure 24). All remaining 14 communities had viable fire trajectories at the 1–km segment length (Figure 25), and of the three segment lengths investigated, these were the most informative for illustrating viable fire trajectories and therefore the directional vulnerability of communities. See Appendix M for the full set of radial graphs produced.

Figure 23. Directional vulnerability assessment radial graphs with 5–km segment length.

Two communities with viable fire trajectories identified using 5–km segment length (short–range exposure; summer hazard classification): (a) Burley and Burley Street; (b) Bransgore and Thorney Hill.

Red lines 0–5 km; orange lines 5–10 km; yellow lines 10–15 km.

(a) Burley and Burley Street (b) Bransgore and Thorney Hill (c) Ringwood, Ashley Heath, Hightown and Hangersley

Figure 24. Directional vulnerability assessment radial graphs with 3–km segment length.

Example communities with viable fire trajectories identified using 3–km segment length (short–range exposure; summer hazard classification): (a) Burley and Burley Street; (b) Bransgore and Thorney Hill; (c) Ringwood, Ashley Heath, Hightown and Hangersley.

Red lines 0–3 km; orange lines 3–6 km; yellow lines 6–9 km.

(a) Burley and Burley Street (b) Bransgore and Thorney Hill (c) Ringwood, Ashley Heath, Hightown and Hangersley

Figure 25. Directional vulnerability assessment radial graphs with 1–km segment length.

Example communities with viable fire trajectories identified using 1–km segment length (short–range exposure; summer hazard classification): (a) Burley and Burley Street; (b) Bransgore and Thorney Hill; (c) Ringwood, Ashley Heath, Hightown and Hangersley.

Red lines 0–1 km; orange lines 1–2 km; yellow lines 2–3 km.

The 1–km segment length was deemed to be most informative due to its greater detail but 5–km can be useful for highlighting dominant trajectories for particularly vulnerable communities, such as Burley and Burley Street (Figure 26).

Figure 26. Comparison of directional vulnerability assessment radial graphs for the same community with different segment lengths.

Comparison of the outputs for the Burley and Burley Street community for all three segment lengths (5 km, 3 km and 1 km), displayed proportionately.

3.4 Synthesis and Framework for Strategic Wildfire Risk Assessment at the Community Scale

The results of the research questions (Table 7) indicated the most appropriate inputs for the various parameters (Table 8) for use in a community-scale directional vulnerability assessment of Dorset-Hampshire (Appendix I.9). A community-scale analysis was conducted on 13 communities and two environmental values (Table 9; Figures 27–29).

Table 7. Research questions, associated baseline parameters, and the results of this study.

Research Question		Published Research	Study Results
1. Wildfire Exposure Assessment (WEA)	Q1a. What is the most suitable land cover resolution for landscape-scale WEAs?	100 m, 30 m	100 m for time efficiency 30 m for detail
	Q1b. What is the most suitable land cover resolution for community-scale WEAs?	30 m, 10 m, 5 m, 3 m	10 m provided adequate detail
	Q1c. What threshold of fire exposure defines high-exposure areas?	60%	80%
		45%: individual telecommunications towers	
30%: in the built environment			
2. Seasonal Hazard Classification	Q2a. What are the hazard classifications for spring and summer?	Canadian Fire Behaviour Prediction System / Alberta Wildfire; Alaska Wildland Fire Coordinating Group (2018) Fuel Model Guide; peer-reviewed literature and local expert panel	peer-reviewed academic studies, grey literature, and local expert panel
	Q2b. Which seasonal hazard classification is most appropriate for use in WEAs?	combined at coarser resolutions; spring for finer resolutions	summer, though combined gives the same result
3. Directional Vulnerability Assessment (DVA)	Q3a. What percentage of a given fire trajectory overlaps high exposure?	80%	100%
	Q3b. What fire transmission distances are appropriate?	long-range embers 500 m short-range embers 100 m radiant heat 30 m	long-range not validated short-range embers 100 m radiant heat not tested
	Q3c. What is the optimal DVA segment length?	5 km	1 km

Table 8. Parameters and inputs used in the directional vulnerability assessments for the Dorset–Hampshire study area.

Research Question	Parameter	Input
	land cover dataset	UKCEH Land Cover Map (2023)
	area of interest	Dorset–Hampshire polygon
Q1b	resolution	10 m
Q1c	high exposure definition	80%
Q2a, Q2b	hazard classification	summer
	viable fire trajectory delineation	spine trajectories (<i>Thin</i> tool in ArcGIS Pro)
Q3a	viable fire trajectory threshold	100%
Q3b	transmission distance	short–range exposure, 100 m
Q3c	radial graph segment length	1 km

Table 9. Abbreviations used for the value polygons in the directional vulnerability assessments.

Area	Abbreviation	Full Names
Dorset	BCP <i>et al.</i>	Bournemouth, Christchurch, Poole, Merritown, Matchams, West Moors, Ferndown, West Parley, Wimborne Minster, Merley and Corfe Mullen
	Dorchester	Dorchester
	Wareham	Wareham
New Forest	BBS	Burley and Burley Street
	Beaulieu	Beaulieu
	BransThorn	Bransgore and Thorney Hill
	Brockenhurst	Brockenhurst
	East Boldre	East Boldre
	Lymington <i>et al.</i>	Lymington, Walhampton, Portmore, Pilley and Mount Pleasant
	Lyndhurst	Lyndhurst
	Ringwood <i>et al.</i>	Ringwood, Ashley Heath, Hightown and Hangersley
	Sandy Down	Sandy Down
Sway	Sway	
environmental values	PI	Puckpits Inclosure (conifer plantation)
	FCS	Forest Central South (conservation area)

The three Dorset DVA radial graphs providing a baseline comparison showed limited vulnerabilities (Figure 27) compared with the New Forest, which revealed greater vulnerabilities (Figure 28). Figure 28 illustrates the interplay of trajectories between the communities, highlighting the value of analysing a group of communities as a whole compared to individual communities, as in Figure 27.

Sources: IGN, Esri UK, Esri, HERE, Garmin, INCREMENT P, USGS, METI/ NASA, NGA, Office for National Statistics licensed under the Open Government Licence v.3.0, contains OS data (c) Crown copyright and database right 2025.

Figure 27. Map of directional vulnerability assessment radial graphs for three communities in Dorset. Red lines 0–1 km; orange lines 1–2 km; yellow lines 2–3 km.

Sources: IGN, Esri UK, Esri, HERE, Garmin, INCREMENT P, USGS, METI/ NASA, NGA, Office for National Statistics licensed under the Open Government Licence v.3.0, contains OS data (c) Crown copyright and database right 2025.

Figure 28. Map of directional vulnerability assessment radial graphs for 10 communities in the New Forest. Red lines 0–1 km; orange lines 1–2 km; yellow lines 2–3 km.

Figure 29 illustrates that the DVA can be applied to environmental values, such as timber and conservation areas, in addition to communities. An analysis reveals an interplay between the vulnerability of the plantation from the north (red trajectories) and north–west (yellow and orange trajectories), and its own contribution to the vulnerability of the conservation area to its west (yellow

and red trajectories within the PI polygon). It also illustrates that Lyndhurst, itself a conservation area, is not vulnerable to its west, despite its proximity to the hazardous coniferous fuel.

Figure 29. Map of directional vulnerability assessment radial graphs for one community and two environmental values in the New Forest.

Red lines 0–1 km; orange lines 1–2 km; yellow lines 2–3 km.

The DVA also highlights that the main road passing through the New Forest, the A31, is vulnerable. Orange (1–2 km) and yellow (2–3 km) trajectories from Ringwood *et al.* and BBS cross the A31 north–east of Ringwood (Figure 28) and trajectories from the plantation and conservation area cross the road north–west of the plantation (Figure 29).

Figure 30 illustrates the first known adaptation of the directional vulnerability assessment to a temperate–deciduous context, and of a synthesis of radial graphs to provide a holistic analysis of a landscape.

Sources: Forest Research, Historic England, Office for National Statistics licensed under the Open Government Licence v.3.0, contains OS data (c) Crown copyright and database right 2025.

Figure 30. Map of directional vulnerability assessment radial graphs for 10 communities and two environmental values in the New Forest.

Red lines 0–1 km; orange lines 1–2 km; yellow lines 2–3 km.

A synthesis of DVAs identifies single localised areas of high exposure causing multiple vulnerabilities that are not apparent from individual radial graphs (Appendix M) and enables the comparison of viable fire trajectories to reveal which are compounded by neighbouring trajectories, leading to multiple values at risk. In Figure 31, the right-hand panels generalise the radial graph transects to highlight the dominant viable fire trajectories to provide a simplified overview to support interpretation and analysis: Figure 31a illustrates an area contributing to a vulnerability of four communities; Figure 31b shows that the lower trajectory entering East Boldre is compounded by a trajectory towards Lymington *et al.*; and Figure 31c shows that while there are trajectories entering BBS from the north and south-west, there are areas causing dual vulnerabilities to its north-west and south.

(a) Brockenhurst, Sway, Sandy Down, and Lymington *et al.* (scale 1:30,000)

(b) East Boldre and Lymington *et al.* (scale 1:30,000)

(c) Burley and Burley Street, Ringwood *et al.*, and Bransgore and Thorney Hill (scale 1:72,000)

Figure continues on next page

Figure 31 (continued)

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Figure 31. Diagrams of directional vulnerability assessment radial graph intersections and generalised dominant viable fire trajectories.

Diagrams of directional vulnerability assessment radial graph intersections (left) and generalised dominant viable fire trajectories (right) for the areas between (a) Brockenhurst, Sway, Sandy Down, and Lymington *et al.*; (b) East Boldre and Lymington *et al.*; and (c) Burley and Burley Street, Ringwood *et al.*, and Bransgore and Thorney Hill. Lines and arrows: red 0–1 km; orange 1–2 km; yellow 2–3 km.

4. Discussion

4.1 Principal Findings

The outcomes for the null hypotheses are as follows.

- 1. Wildfire exposure.** The null hypothesis that fires do not occur preferentially in high–exposure areas was rejected for short–range exposure (100 m) as validation results showed a surplus of burned cells in high–exposure classes. For long–range exposure (500 m, 300 m and 200 m), the null hypotheses could not be rejected as fires occurred preferentially in the Nil exposure class.
- 2. Fire trajectories.** The null hypothesis that fire trajectories do not intersect high–exposure areas for most of their length was rejected as the majority (61%) of fire trajectories exhibited 100% overlap with high–exposure areas. This result confirms that fire trajectories are strongly associated with high–exposure areas.
- 3. Parameters.** The null hypothesis that assessment parameters have no significant effect on results was rejected as results demonstrated sensitivity to seasonal hazard classification, transmission distance, and DVA segment length.

These findings show that the unmodified DVA is not informative for decision making in the English context and that a customised short–range exposure DVA is informative for community–scale wildfire risk assessments, particularly when using a 1–km segment length. The ease of adjusting the segment length parameter in the R script also means that it can be varied to suit the analysis, providing flexibility in interpreting results. The variation in neighbouring DVA results, ranging from negligible (e.g. Tiptoe *et al.*) to substantial (e.g. BBS), highlights that the assessment provides differentiated information at the local scale rather than a uniform outcome, supporting its use for wildfire risk assessment.

The results align with exposure–validation studies showing that wildfires burn preferentially in high–exposure areas (Schmidt *et al.*, 2024; Khan *et al.*, 2025b) and diverge from research in boreal ecosystems that emphasise longer transmission distances (Kim *et al.*, 2024; Kuiper and Beverly, 2025). They also support the DVA as a community–scale risk assessment tool used for planning and mitigation rather than real–time prediction (e.g. FSim and European statistical models), reinforcing the value of exposure–based metrics when long–term and dynamic forecasts are uncertain (Beverly *et al.*, 2021).

Beyond communities and environmental values, the DVA identified a vulnerable transport corridor, consistent with the evacuation–scenario evaluation described by Kim *et al.* (2024). This accords with Veeraswamy *et al.* (2018), who simulated urban–scale evacuation scenarios following the 2011 Swinley Forest fire. The approach also extends to infrastructure assets such as electricity pylons and telecommunications masts, as shown by Kuiper and Beverly (2025).

Although long–range exposure was not validated for England, the findings on data resolution and hazard classification are applicable to Scotland and Wales, subject to validation.

4.2 Methodological Innovations

Two novel methods for delineating viable fire trajectories in ArcGIS Pro were investigated, and an original R script was developed for the DVA validation (Step 4).

The two methods for delineating viable fire trajectories produced straight flowlines and curved spines. While the flowlines were consistent with the manually delineated trajectories in the published literature (Beverly and Forbes, 2023), the spines were more representative of the fire behaviour and trajectories in England, which tend to be more multidirectional and fragmented, and less elliptical and wind–driven compared with Canadian wildfires.

Although intended for narrow linear features such as rivers, the *Thin* tool used to generate fire polygon spines is straightforward to apply, enabling easier automation and reproducibility, compared with flowlines, which were more complicated to produce. While both methods were validated, there was generally a greater total length of spine trajectories intersecting high–exposure areas, supporting the choice of spines for subsequent analyses. The spine–based method provides a scalable, objective option to model viable fire trajectories without subjective manual delineation or sampling.

The original R script developed for the DVA validation also provides a simpler alternative for future validations through improved reproducibility and reduced processing time.

4.3 Validations

Both the short-range WEA and the viable fire trajectories were validated, aligning with previous research (Beverly *et al.*, 2010). This suggests that the short-range DVA captures the vegetative fuel patterns characteristic of temperate, fragmented landscapes and supports their use in the English landscape.

The lack of validation for long-range exposure in England reflects the low proportion of fuels capable of supporting long-range ember transport, such as heather and conifers (McMorrow *et al.*, 2021), highlighting the importance of avoiding generalisation across ecosystems, and suggesting that the results of this study are not directly applicable to other areas of the UK.

Conservative options were consistently chosen to prioritise public safety and ecological resilience. The aim of the study's assessments was not to predict wildfire trajectories but to identify potential vulnerabilities and support targeted mitigation efforts, which aligns with the DVA's use as an exposure-based planning tool for community-scale decision making (Beverly and Forbes, 2023).

4.4 Adaptation to the English Context

The results revealed differences from the published research (Table 7): the lack of validation for long-range exposure; a higher threshold (80%) for defining high-exposure areas compared with 60% or less (Beverly *et al.*, 2010, 2021; Kuiper and Beverly, 2025); a greater overlap of high-exposure areas with viable fire trajectories, i.e. 100% versus 80% (Beverly and Forbes, 2023); and shorter segment length for DVA radial graphs, i.e. 1 km compared with 5 km (e.g. Kim *et al.*, 2024). In England, the dominance of deciduous trees and grasslands reduces the potential for long-range exposure; fires are generally smaller, patchier, less intense, have more meandering trajectories, and are more easily interrupted by changes in vegetation, such as hedges surrounding arable fields (Tasker and Wentworth, 2024). These differences align with the contrast in fire regimes between temperate deciduous and boreal ecosystems, which explains why the DVA had to be modified to be informative in the English context.

4.5 Wider Applicability to Temperate Deciduous Ecosystems

Despite the contextual differences outlined above, the successful validation and synthesis of results demonstrate that the DVA is sufficiently robust and flexible to be adapted for use in the temperate deciduous ecosystem, where fires are typically infrequent, patchy, short range, and strongly influenced by human land use and ignitions (Berčák *et al.*, 2024). This has implications for wildfire risk assessment in other temperate deciduous regions in Europe, North America and East Asia, where wildfire dynamics are similarly shaped by fragmented land use, heterogeneous fuel structures and human ignitions (Hanberry, 2020; Stoof *et al.*, 2024; Kim *et al.*, 2025).

The capacity to recalibrate parameters locally while retaining the same framework underscores the DVA's value as a transferable tool, providing strategic benefit in landscapes where existing risk models, designed for large, high-intensity fire regimes (Wasserman and Mueller, 2023), are less suitable for the smaller, patchier, human-driven fires typical of many temperate deciduous ecosystems.

4.6 Data Inputs

WEAs, and consequently DVAs, are sensitive to the quality of input land cover data (Forbes and Beverly, 2024b). Using a 10-m land cover dataset at its original resolution averted errors that can result when a raster dataset is resampled to a coarser resolution, and was sufficient for the level of analysis, although other studies have used even finer resolutions (Beverly *et al.*, 2010; Khan *et al.*, 2025a).

Burned area data affects WEA validation and, in turn, DVA validation; therefore using different burned area data could change the exposure validation result, high exposure threshold and viable trajectory threshold (Table 4). While the land cover input (2023) post-dates the burned area data (2014–2021), this was not expected to significantly affect the results, given the relatively low severity and rapid vegetation recovery typical of British fires (Tasker and Wentworth, 2024).

The use of nationally available input datasets enables reproducibility of the workflow across England. Adaptation to other parts of the UK will require revalidation of thresholds, exposure distances, and segment lengths to account for regional variations in vegetative fuels, fire regimes, and land use. Although a formal sensitivity analysis was beyond the scope of this study, all key parameters were evidence-based, drawing on literature, expert opinion, or direct validation; segment length was empirically tested to ensure suitability in this context.

4.7 Limitations

Generalisations are necessary when modelling an ecosystem due to the trade-off between ecological reality and operational practicalities. As a proof-of-concept study, there were several limitations: the bespoke hazard classification; the constraint of computer processing capabilities; the limited spatial extent of the study area; and the relatively short timeframe of the data used for validation. Ongoing changes in climate and fire regime also mean that the assessments will need to be periodically revalidated. These limitations indicate areas where future research (Section 4.9) could improve the quality of input data and extend the spatial and temporal aspects of the assessments.

4.8 Implications and Applications

Applications of the DVA are as follows:

- **Forest management plans.** For forest managers, the DVA identifies vulnerable approach trajectories into and out of the management area; prioritises fuel-treatment locations for mitigation; and supports emergency preparedness by identifying ingress/egress points, access and evacuation routes, water-supply points, and safety zones.
- **Policy.** The short-range DVA directly serves the UK Forestry Standard guidance to assess wildfire risk in the forest management plan and to maintain operational and contingency plans (Forest Research, 2023).
- **Fuel treatment.** The DVA identifies viable fire-entry trajectories into communities and environmental values, supporting scenario testing of treatment location, extent and sequencing. Land managers can prioritise prescribed burning and other treatments to disrupt these pathways within the 0–3 km approach sectors and at key ingress points.
- **Transport and evacuation routes.** DVA radial graphs identify where potential wildfire trajectories intersect vulnerable transport corridors and evacuation routes, supporting scenario planning.
- **Infrastructure.** The DVA can be extended to infrastructure assets such as electricity pylons and telecommunications masts.
- **Communities.** The DVA can inform local communities regarding their rural-urban interface, such as the management of road verges, hedges and fuel breaks at likely ingress points.
- **Wind direction.** Prevailing west-southwest (WSW) winds indicate greater vulnerability for values whose radial graphs show DVA trajectories (0–3 km) oriented towards them (e.g. BBS) for both spring and summer (observations for [EGHH] Bournemouth, 1973–2020; Iowa Environmental Mesonet, 2025)

- **Human-caused ignitions.** The DVA highlights areas for targeted public education, fire prevention, and fire-fighting equipment. For example, where a viable fire trajectory overlaps with recreational use, such as a campsite, signage, water points and fire-fighting equipment can be increased.
- **Stakeholder use.** The DVA provides a risk assessment resource for agencies such as Forestry England, New Forest National Park Authority, Hampshire and Isle of Wight Fire and Rescue Service, Hampshire County Council and National Highways. It supports incident planning, multi-agency exercises and resource allocation to the most vulnerable community and environmental values.
- **Ease of use.** The DVA is data-light and reproducible, requiring only the land-cover raster and a value polygon (or point). After a short training session, practitioners can run and update the DVA independently.
- **Training.** The DVA can be incorporated into pre-existing vegetation fire training, such as the Forestry Commission's Lantra-accredited course (Forestry Commission, 2025).
- **Scalability.** Availability of national 10-m resolution land cover data enables the DVA for short-range exposure to be applied at scale across England to additional communities and environmental values.
- **Risk assessment.** The DVA provides a spatially explicit and directional basis for assessing wildfire risk by identifying where values are most exposed to potential fire encroachment. This enables comparison of relative vulnerability between locations and supports prioritisation of mitigation resources.
- **Insurance.** The DVA provides spatially explicit evidence of wildfire exposure and viable trajectories, supporting insurers in evaluating risk for assets. By identifying wildfire pathways and ingress points, the DVA can inform premium setting, underwriting, and incentives for risk-reduction measures such as fuel treatments and strategic vegetation plantings.

4.9 Future Research

To strengthen the evidence base, refine parameter choices, and test transferability before operational rollout, further work should address the following:

- **Hazard classifications and transmission distances.** Improve the confidence level of the hazard classifications with interviews of experts and field evidence, and confirm that summer is the most appropriate classification to use.

- **Extend WEA validation.** Lengthen the validation period and triangulate burned–area datasets, such as remote sensing and incident records, to confirm the exposure validation result and high exposure threshold.
- **Number of transects.** The fireexposuR package uses the radial graph default of 360 transects (one every 1°) but this can be adjusted to produce more (every 0.5°) or less (every 2°) depending on the detail required.
- **Elliptical–spread assumptions.** Classical elliptical fire spread models (Van Wagner, 1969; Albini, 1976) presuppose continuous, homogeneous fuels and therefore more research could investigate how to better represent fire spread within fragmented, heterogeneous fuels.
- **Fire–trajectory method.** Develop the spine method: standardising the parameters and testing with alternative burned area data and study areas.
- **R script verification.** Ask an independent researcher to run the code on different datasets and in a second study area, and confirm the outputs match the expected results.
- **Geographic expansion.** Validate long– and short–range exposure in Scotland, Wales and Ireland, and other temperate deciduous ecosystems, to assess applicability. Determine whether long–range exposure is validated in other areas in England that have a greater proportion of hazardous fuels, such as the upland moorlands of northern England.
- **Change over time.** Repeat the analysis for earlier periods (e.g. using UKCEH data from 1990) to detect temporal change and discuss implications for future conditions.
- **Radiant heat.** Determine whether radiant heat exposure is validated and run the DVA on values of interest at the local scale, comparing and contrasting with the short–range exposure DVA results.
- **Land cover data.** Use improved datasets derived from advances in remote sensing to increase assessment accuracy. Conduct local surveys to support DVA outputs and their interpretations, since ground–truthing of land cover data is cost–prohibitive at the landscape scale.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrated the successful adaptation of the directional vulnerability assessment in England, confirming its customisability across geographic areas and fire regimes (Beverly and Forbes, 2023). Results found that fires burn preferentially in high–exposure areas and that fire trajectories intersect areas of high exposure, validating the DVA. A modified, short–range exposure DVA was validated and is informative at the community scale, and a 1–km segment length in the DVA radial graph was most informative. A new and reproducible ArcGIS Pro method and R script reduced subjectivity and processing time. Operationally, the DVA is data–light and easy to use,

requiring only the 10 m land–cover raster, a point/polygon for the value, the R script, and minimal training. These findings support targeted short– and long–term mitigation planning and emergency preparedness by forest managers and other stakeholders, and align with UK government policy guidance.

Declaration of Funding

The author received financial support from the International Association of Wildland Fire (IAWF) and the Scottish Forestry Trust to attend the fireexposuR training workshop at the IAWF’s Wildland Fire Canada Conference in Fredericton, NB, Canada. No sources had any involvement in the preparation of the data or manuscript.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Acknowledgements

I am like a child perched on the shoulders of a giant.

after William of Conches, 1123

My dissertation was only possible due to the work of Jen Beverly and Air Forbes in Canada, and I am eternally grateful to them for their enthusiastic support of my research.

In the UK, I have greatly benefited from the support of:

Dr Rob Gazzard, Advisor on Contingency Planning & Wildfire at the Forestry Commission;
Andy Elliott, Senior Research Fellow in Wildfire at University of Exeter, Managing Director at Wildfire Training & Consultancy, formerly with the Dorset & Wiltshire Fire & Rescue Service;
Robert Stacey, Wildfire Team Leader and Project Officer at Northumberland Fire and Rescue Service;
and my supervisor at Bangor University, Dr James Gibbons, Senior Lecturer in Ecological Modelling and Dean of Research for the College, School of Environmental & Natural Sciences.

A huge thank you to the anonymous vegetation fire fighters who took the time to complete my questionnaire.

A big shout out to my IAWF community for their friendship and enthusiasm – Becky D’Arcy, Fiona Newman–Thacker, Patrick Robinson, Jinhan Xie, Joe Rakofsky, John Davies, Meg Dolman, Mark Newman – and to my fellow team members at the Wildfire Analytics research lab, University of Alberta.

For financial support, my appreciation goes to:

- The International Association of Wildland Fire (IAWF) and Scottish Forestry Trust (SFT) for enabling me to attend the IAWF Tralee and the Fredericton conferences.
- The Institute of Chartered Foresters (ICF) and Confederation of Forest Industries (Confor) for enabling me to do the Forestry Commission/Lantra Vegetation Fire Foundation, Wildfire Management Plan, Vegetation Fire Operator and Prescribed Fire Manager courses.

My personal thanks go to Dan Holloway for his unwavering support and to Jamie for being my ray of golden sunshine.

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Appendix A. Presentation requirements

A.1 Relevant Bangor University requirements

The dissertation should use clear and continuous page numbering (bottom of page).

The main body of the text should:

- be a minimum of 12–point font for all text including footnotes
- 1.5 line spacing
- text alignment should be justified.

A.2 Relevant International Journal of Wildland Fire requirements¹⁰

Style

- Use sentence case for text within figures.
- Use 'and' not '&'.
- For ranges in numbers (5–10) or minus signs (–20) please use an en rule rather than a hyphen as this is clearer for the reader.
- Spell out numbers lower than 10 unless accompanied by a unit of measure, e.g. 2 mm, 15 mm, two plants, 15 plants. Do not leave a space between a numeral and the unit % or °C.
- Type the title of each table as a separate paragraph from the table. Put explanatory matter referring to the table as a whole in the headnote, which should be a separate paragraph from the table title.

Keywords. A minimum of 8 keywords are recommended to increase article discoverability via online searches.

Acknowledgements. Place Acknowledgements after the Discussion and before the References.

Conflicts of Interest. A ‘Conflicts of Interest’ section should be included at the end of the manuscript. It should identify any financial or non–financial (political, personal, professional) interests/relationships that may be interpreted to have influenced the manuscript.

Declaration of Funding. Under a subheading ‘Declaration of Funding’ at the end of the text authors are required to declare all sources of funding for the research and/or preparation of the article. Authors should declare sponsor names along with explanations of the role of those sources if any in the preparation of the data or manuscript or the decision to submit for publication; or a statement declaring that the supporting source had no such involvement.

¹⁰ www.publish.csiro.au/wf/forauthors/AuthorInstructions

Appendix B. Long-range exposure validation for Great Britain and Scotland

The comparison between expected (dashed bar) and observed (solid bar) burned area proportion for long-range exposure (500 m transmission distance) for Great Britain revealed the largest surplus of burned cells in the Nil exposure class (Figure B1a). For Scotland, it revealed a large surplus of burned cells in the 0.6–1.0 exposure class (Figure B1b). The long-range WEA is validated for Scotland, despite not being validated for Great Britain as a whole.

(a) Great Britain

Figure continues on next page

Figure B1 (continued)

(b) Scotland

Figure B1. Comparison between expected and observed burned area across exposure class for long-range exposure for Great Britain and Scotland.

Comparison between expected (dashed bar) and observed (solid bar) burned area across exposure class (summer hazard classification) using a 0.5% sample (left) and total (right): (a) Great Britain and (b) Scotland.

Appendix C. UKCEH Land Cover Map 2023 (10 m)

Figure C1. UKCEH Land Cover Map 2023 (10 m) and land–cover classes (Morton *et al.*, 2024a).

Appendix D. Seasonal hazard classification literature review

Seasonal hazard classification references retrieved via a literature review:

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- Gagkas, Z., Rivington, M., Glendell, M., Gimona, A. and Martino, S. (2023) *Fire danger assessment of Scottish habitat types. Deliverable 2.3b for the Project D5-2 Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital*. Aberdeen: The James Hutton Institute. Available at: https://www.hutton.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/Deliverable-D2_3b-Fire-Danger-Fuels-Final-6-3-23.pdf.
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- The Scottish Government (2013) *FRS Wildfire Operational Guidance*. Edinburgh: The Scottish Government. Available at: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/fire-rescue-service-wildfire-operational-guidance/documents/>.

Additional seasonal hazard classification references used in AI-assisted deep research:

- ✓ Retrievable
- ✗ Non-retrievable

National wildfire guidance documents:

- ✗ Scottish Fire and Rescue Service (2023). *Scottish Wildfire Forum: Wildfire Operational Guidance*. [Internal document]
- ✓ Taylor, A.F.S., Bruce, M., Britton, A.J., Owen, I.J., Gagkas, Z., Pohle, I., Fielding, D. and Hadden, R. (2021) *Fire Danger Rating System (FDRS) Report*. Aberdeen: James Hutton Institute. Available at: <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/publications/SFDRS-Research-Report-Final-15-2-2022.pdf>.

- ✘ Davies, G. M., *et al.* (2010). *Fire prevention and control on open habitats in the UK.*

Wildfire risk assessment frameworks for peatland and grassland fuels:

- ✘ Natural England (2021). *The Peatland Wildfire Risk Assessment Framework.* [Precursor framework, indirectly referenced.]

UK wildfire incident records:

- ✘ Natural England (2016). *Understanding the impacts of wildfires in England.* Natural England Evidence Review NERR064.
- ✘ McMorrow, J., *et al.* (2023). *Scottish Fire Danger Rating System: Technical Report.* The James Hutton Institute & Scottish Government.
- ✘ Hutton Institute (2020). *Large Wildfire Incidents in the UK: Statistical Analysis 2013–2019.* [Internal report]

Fire weather seasonality:

- ✓ UK Met Office. Fire Severity Index (FSI).
<https://experience.arcgis.com/experience/328554206f114fc98c707bfc1b880cf7/page/Business-Page?dlg=FSI-Instructions&views=Further-Information-->

Vegetation classifications:

- ✓ UKCEH (2020) ‘The UKCEH Land Cover Maps for 2017, 2018 and 2019 (Product Documentation v1.5.1)’.

Framework & Model Sources

- ✓ Beverly, J.L., Bothwell, P., Conner, J. and Herd, E. (2010) ‘Assessing the exposure of the built environment to potential ignition sources generated from vegetative fuel’, *International Journal of Wildland Fire*, 19, pp. 299–313. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1071/WF09071>.
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Appendix E. Seasonal hazard classification expert opinion questionnaire

E.1 Favourable opinion from Research Ethics Committee

College of Environmental Science & Engineering AREC

PMYA Coleg Gwyddorau'r Amgylchedd a Pheirianeg

PRIFYSGOL
BANGOR
UNIVERSITY

13/02/2025

Astudiaeth / Study: Developing a directional-vulnerability wildfire risk assessment for British forest managers
Cyf. / Ref.: 0635

Annwyl James

Dear James

Diolch am gyflwyno'r astudiaeth uchod er mwyn cynnal adolygiad moeseg ymchwil.

Thank you for your submission for research ethics review of the above study.

Ein plaser yw dweud i ni ddod i fam ffafriol am yr astudiaeth.

We are pleased to provide a favourable opinion of the study.

Bydd y fam ffafriol yn parhau'n ddilys tan ddyddiad dod i ben yr astudiaeth, sef 31/08/2025. Sylwch fod y fam hon yn berthnasol i'r astudiaeth fel y'i disgrifir yn eich cyflwyniad ac y bydd angen cyflwyno unrhyw ddiwygiadau i weithdrefnau neu brosesau'r astudiaeth i'w hystyried gan y pwyllgor ymlaen llaw, cyn iddynt gael eu mabwysiadu.

The favourable opinion will remain valid until the stated study end date of 31/08/2025. Please note that this opinion applies to the study as it is described in your submission and that any amendments to the study procedures or processes need to be submitted for consideration by the committee in advance, before they are adopted.

Mae croeso i chi gysylltu os oes gennych unrhyw gwestiynau pellach.

Please contact me if you have any further questions.

Dymunwn yn dda i chi gyda'ch astudiaethau a'ch ymchwil.

We wish you well with your study and research.

Cofion gwresog

Kind regards

Cadeirydd - PMYA Coleg Gwyddorau'r Amgylchedd a Pheirianeg

Chair - College of Environmental Science & Engineering AREC

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E.2 Online questionnaire

Spreading Like Wildfire: Developing a directional vulnerability wildfire risk assessment

Introduction I am conducting a research dissertation for my MSc Forestry at Bangor University, collecting expert opinions from UK vegetation fire fighters on hazard classification of vegetation land cover types. The data will be used in the R package 'fireexposuR' to create wildfire exposure maps and directional vulnerability radial graphs, adapting a Canadian methodology (Beverly & Forbes, 2023) for the British landscape.

Purpose of the Research This project aims to adapt directional vulnerability wildfire assessments for the UK, creating a tool for forest managers to improve strategic planning and wildfire resilience.

Your Participation You will be asked 4 questions regarding your professional experience as a vegetation fire fighter, and then 6 more regarding your expert opinion on whether different vegetation land covers could ignite further fires from varying distances by the mechanisms of radiant heat, short-range embers and long-range embers. The questionnaire does not collect any personally-identifying data so your answers will be submitted anonymously. All 10 questions are optional, and the questionnaire should not take long to complete.

Voluntary participation You are being invited to take part in this research because you have been suggested by a colleague as someone who has sufficient professional experience of fighting vegetation fires in the UK to be able to give an expert opinion. Your involvement is voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time without giving a reason. If withdrawn, all data, including e-mail correspondence, will be deleted.

Use and Storage of Data The information regarding your fire fighting experience will be used to calculate the weighting given to your answer in comparison to answers from other experts, should the answers differ. The information given regarding the ability of different vegetation land covers to ignite further fires will be collated with other answers to create a binary classification that will be fed into the R script in order to run the assessments. Data will be stored securely on my Bangor University OneDrive, accessible only to me, and will be deleted in September 2025.

Benefits and Sharing Results There is no financial benefit, but your participation will support my research and will support wildfire risk assessment improvements. The dissertation will be submitted to Bangor University, and a copy can be provided upon request. If published, I can inform you upon request.

Research Ethics This project is approved by the Bangor University Ethics Committee (Reference: 2025/0635/3) with no conflicts of interest.

Questions If you have any questions at any point, please don't hesitate to ask me (srw21yxv@bangor.ac.uk) or my supervisor, Dr James Gibbons (j.gibbons@bangor.ac.uk).

Thank you for your time.

1. Consent

The following question is for you, as the Participant, to confirm that you have been given all relevant information about the research, had the opportunity to ask me questions and had any such questions answered satisfactorily, and to confirm your willingness to take part in the research.

Please read through the following statements carefully, and then select Yes to indicate your confirmation of them. If you do not agree to a statement, please stop and contact me so that I can resolve the issue.

1. I confirm that I have read the above information and fully understand the information it contained.
2. I understand that my participation in this research is voluntary. I will not be paid for my involvement. I am free to withdraw from the research at any time, without giving a reason.
3. I have read and understood that all data provided will be anonymous and treated in strictest confidence. I understand that my data will be kept securely until the resulting dissertation is submitted (anticipated to be September 2025) and in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (2016).
4. I understand that this research has been reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the School of Natural and Environmental Sciences, Bangor University (Reference: xxx).
5. I have read and understood the explanation of the research project provided to me. I have had the opportunity to ask any questions and they have been answered to my satisfaction.
6. I agree to take part in this research project.

*

Yes

2. How many years' experience do you have fighting vegetation fires in the UK?

Enter your answer

3. How many vegetation fires have you attended to date? Please estimate if you are not sure.

Enter your answer

4. Thinking about your vegetation fire fighting experience, which land cover types have you had **most experience** with? Tick all that apply.

- Deciduous woodland
- Coniferous woodland
- Arable
- Improved grassland
- Neutral grassland
- Calcareous grassland
- Acid grassland
- Fen
- Heather
- Heather grassland
- Bog

5. Thinking about your vegetation fire fighting experience, which land cover types have you had **least experience** with? Tick all that apply.

- Deciduous woodland
- Coniferous woodland
- Arable
- Improved grassland
- Neutral grassland
- Calcareous grassland
- Acid grassland
- Fen
- Heather
- Heather grassland
- Bog

6. In your professional opinion, does 30 metres away accurately reflect the distance at which a vegetation fire can ignite fuel due to its radiant heat?

If **No**, what distance would you say was more accurate, on average? Please complete the 'Other' box with the distance (in metres).

- Yes
- No
- Other

7. In your professional opinion, does 100 metres away accurately reflect the distance at which a vegetation fire can ignite fuel due to its short-range embers?

If **No**, what distance would you say was more accurate, on average? Please complete the 'Other' box with the distance (in metres).

- Yes
- No
- Other

8. In your professional opinion, does 500 metres away accurately reflect the distance at which a vegetation fire can ignite fuel due to its long-range embers?

If **No**, what distance would you say was more accurate, on average? Please complete the 'Other' box with the distance (in metres).

- Yes
- No
- Other

9. In your professional opinion, based upon your experience of fighting vegetation fires in the UK, are the following vegetation categories in the table below **hazardous** at 30 metres during Spring (March - May)? (i.e. could they ignite further fires from 30 metres away with their radiant heat?) Only select 'NO' if they are **consistently** not hazardous during this season.

If you're not sure because you have not had enough experience with that vegetation type, please select 'Not sure'.

	Spring: YES	Spring: NO	Not sure
Deciduous woodland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Coniferous woodland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Arable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improved grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Neutral grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Calcareous grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Acid grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Heather	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Heather grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bog	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

10. In your professional opinion, based upon your experience of fighting vegetation fires in the UK, are the following vegetation categories in the table below **hazardous** at 30 metres during Summer (June - August)? (i.e. could they ignite further fires from 30 metres away with their radiant heat?) Only select 'NO' if they are **consistently** not hazardous during this season.

If you're not sure because you have not had enough experience with that vegetation type, please select 'Not sure'.

	Summer: YES	Summer: NO	Not sure
Deciduous woodland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Coniferous woodland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Arable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improved grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Neutral grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Calcareous grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Acid grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Heather	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Heather grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bog	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

11. In your professional opinion, based upon your experience of fighting vegetation fires in the UK, are the following vegetation categories in the table below **hazardous** at 100 metres during Spring (March - May)? (i.e. could they ignite further fires from 100 metres away with their short-range embers?) Only select 'NO' if they are **consistently** not hazardous during that season.

If you're not sure because you have not had enough experience with that vegetation type, please select 'Not sure'.

	Spring: YES	Spring: NO	Not sure
Deciduous woodland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Coniferous woodland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Arable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improved grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Neutral grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Calcareous grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Acid grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Heather	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Heather grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bog	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

12. In your professional opinion, based upon your experience of fighting vegetation fires in the UK, are the following vegetation categories in the table below **hazardous** at 100 metres during Summer (June - August)? (i.e. could they ignite further fires from 100 metres away with their short-range embers?) Only select 'NO' if they are **consistently** not hazardous during that season.

If you're not sure because you have not had enough experience with that vegetation type, please select 'Not sure'.

	Summer: YES	Summer: NO	Not sure
Deciduous woodland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Coniferous woodland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Arable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improved grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Neutral grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Calcareous grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Acid grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Heather	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Heather grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bog	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

13. In your professional opinion, based upon your experience of fighting vegetation fires in the UK, are the following vegetation categories in the table below **hazardous** at 500 metres during Spring (March - May)? (i.e. could they ignite further fires from 500 metres away with their long-range embers?) Only select 'NO' if they are **consistently** not hazardous during that season.

If you're not sure because you have not had enough experience with that vegetation type, please select 'Not sure'.

	Spring: YES	Spring: NO	Not sure
Deciduous woodland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Coniferous woodland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Arable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improved grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Neutral grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Calcareous grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Acid grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Heather	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Heather grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bog	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

14. In your professional opinion, based upon your experience of fighting vegetation fires in the UK, are the following vegetation categories in the table below **hazardous** at 500 metres during Summer (June - August)? (i.e. could they ignite further fires from 500 metres away with their long-range embers?) Only select 'NO' if they are **consistently** not hazardous during that season.

If you're not sure because you have not had enough experience with that vegetation type, please select 'Not sure'.

	Summer: YES	Summer: NO	Not sure
Deciduous woodland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Coniferous woodland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Arable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improved grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Neutral grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Calcareous grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Acid grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Heather	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Heather grassland	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bog	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Appendix F. Land–cover classes contributing < 0.1% of burned area

UKCEH land–cover classes that contributed < 0.1% of burned area in the GABAM for Great Britain (2014–21) and therefore classified as non–burnable in the R script for the WEA.

Table F1. Land–cover classes contributing < 0.1% of burned area.

Land Cover ID	Description	Percentage of total burned area, 2014–21
12	Inland rock	0.08%
13	Saltwater	0.00%
14	Freshwater	0.05%
15	Supralittoral rock	0.01%
16	Supralittoral sediment	0.02%
17	Littoral rock	0.00%
18	Littoral sediment	0.00%
19	Saltmarsh	0.09%

Appendix G. Explanatory details of data–preparation flowcharts

G.1 Polygon preparation

- Created a polygon of England and a polygon of Dorset and Hampshire combined from the Counties and Unitary Authorities data.
- As wildfire is a continuous spatial phenomenon, excluded isolated landmasses (islands) from the polygons to produce a single continuous landmass for assessment.
- Due to the WEA involving a neighbourhood analysis with a maximum radius of 500 m, extended the polygons by 600 m to allow for edge cells to be correctly assessed.
- Created polygons, without a buffer zone, for values to be assessed in Dorset and Hampshire from the Built–Up Areas Boundaries, Conservation Areas and National Forest Inventory datasets.
- Simplified polygons for use in fireexposuR, which rejects polygons with detailed edges.
- Merged polygons where the built–up areas were contiguous, for example, Burley and Burley Street.

G.2 Land–cover raster preparation

- The land–cover classifications were converted from text to integers so the raster would function correctly in ArcGIS Pro and R.
- The second band containing confidence data was removed by converting the raster to a single–band raster.
- Gaps in the data around the edge of the landmass were removed by reclassifying the NoData and 0 cells to 13 (saltwater).
- Resampled the 10 m resolution data to create rasters at 30 m, 50 m, and 100 m resolutions. Majority aggregation was used to preserve the dominant class in the categorical data.
- Coarser resolutions were not required because, in order to capture spatial heterogeneity and prevent blunt results during the neighbourhood analysis, the coarsest usable resolution is one–third of the transmission distance, i.e. for a 500 m transmission distance, 166 m resolution data are the coarsest that can be used.
- Clipped the rasters to England and to the Dorset–Hampshire area using the appropriate polygon (details above).
- Exported rasters to GeoTIFF files.

G.3 Burned area raster preparation

- Merged the five tiles from the same year into one raster, ensuring that the coordinate system of the new rasters matched that of the land–cover raster.
- Clipped each annual raster to the England polygon and converted to a binary raster.
- Merged all annual rasters into one, converted the burned areas into burn polygons, merging chronologically separate but spatially overlapping burns.
- Clipped back burn polygons by one cell (30 m) to reduce edge effects and remove burned areas < 0.36 ha.

Appendix H. Two methods investigating automatic delineation of viable fire trajectories

When manually delineating viable fire trajectories, previous research used criteria to support decision making: each trajectory is linear; a minimum of 1,000 m; at least 50 m from the fire perimeter; and sampling only fires > 100 ha (Beverly and Forbes, 2023). This method was deemed inappropriate for the English burned area data for two reasons: first, the lack of large, fast-moving, wind-driven fires across fairly homogenous vegetation cover meant that linear trajectories are less likely to accurately reflect the slower, less intense fires across the more heterogenous vegetation cover in England; second, there are too few fires > 100 ha to provide a large enough sample; and third, the large number of small fires meant that manual delineation would be time-prohibitive. Consequently, a novel approach was investigated to automate identification of fire trajectories using ArcGIS Pro toolsets that offered the added advantage of removing the inherent subjectivity of manual delineation. Preliminary analysis involved trials of two candidate methods using the Dorset burn perimeters and the GB burned area data.

H.1 Methods

Flowlines

- Converted each raster of annual burned area to a polygon vector layer. This was done for each annual raster to prevent overlaps from creating false fire trajectories.
- Created rectangles around each polygon, calculated the midpoint of the shortest sides, and joined them with a straight line.
- Clipped back the flowlines using the clipped-back burn polygons (Appendix G.3, point 4) to reduce edge effects.

Spines

- Using the *Thin* tool in ArcGIS Pro, stripped back the sides of each burned area to form a medial axis, like a spine. Annual rasters were processed individually to prevent overlaps from creating false fire trajectories.
- Converted each raster to polylines, then merged into a single vector layer.
- Clipped back the polylines using the clipped-back burn polygons (Appendix G.3, point 4) to reduce edge effects.

H.2 Results

The spines were thought to more accurately reflect the multiple trajectories of less intense, slower moving vegetation fires within non-elliptical shapes compared to the fires of the Canadian boreal ecosystem where the flowlines are more appropriate.

(a) Flowline (brown line)

(b) Spine (blue line)

Figure H1. Comparison of a flowline and a spine in a burned area.

Comparison of (a) flowline (brown line) and (b) spine (blue line) in a burned area (pale orange) near Brockhill, Dorset, 2015; burned area 19 ha, moderate wind, medium fire intensity (pers. comm., Elliott, 2025). Length of polygon 1,040 m, width approximately 200 m. White, green and blue represent land cover from the underlying topographic map (Esri UK).

H.3 Validation

Validation (Step 4) showed that there was generally a greater intersect between the spines and high-exposure areas than between the flowlines and high-exposure areas. Therefore, the *Thin* method, which produces spines, was chosen as the more appropriate and conservative option.

(a) Dorset burned area data and 10 m resolution data (short-range exposure)

(b) GB burned area data and 30 m resolution data (short-range exposure)

Figure H2. Frequency of fire trajectories by percentage of trajectory length intersection with high exposure areas for flowlines and spines. Validation results (Step 4) comparing flowlines (left) and spines (right) at short-range exposure: (a) Dorset burned area data and 10 m resolution data and (b) GB burned area data and 30 m resolution data.

Table H1. Validation results comparing flowlines and spines.

Validation results (Step 4) comparing flowlines and spines, using the Dorset burn perimeters and the GB burned area data.

	Flowlines	Spines
Dorset burned area data	mean percent 76.87 median percent 100 percent high exposure 84.79	mean percent 86.77 median percent 100 percent high exposure 85.07
GB burned area data	mean percent 75.61 median percent 100 percent high exposure 82.33	mean percent 80.06 median percent 100 percent high exposure 80.23

Appendix I. R scripts

I.1 WEA template – spring

```
# R script template 1 exposure
# Task no. {task}, Scale {scale}; Season {season}, Resolution {resolution}m, Range
{range}, Transmission distance {tdist}

# 1. check R, R Studio and fireexposuR are all up-to-date
# 2. check I have devtools
# 3. set my working directory
setwd("C:/Users/sarah/Documents/R Projects/2025")

# 4. load required libraries
library(fireexposuR)
library(terra)

# 5. read raster data to create: (scale)(resolution)_fuel
{scale}{resolution}_fuel <- rast("{scale}/{resolution}/{scale}_{resolution}m.tif")

# 6. read vector data
area_of_interest <- vect("{scale}/{scale}_aoi.shp")

# 7. plot to see them
plot({scale}{resolution}_fuel)
plot(area_of_interest)

# 8. create a hazard reclassification matrix for the season:
(scale)(resolution)_(range)_matrix_(season)
# Ensure the binary classifications are for spring.
{scale}{resolution}_(range)_matrix_{season} <- matrix(c(1, 0, #Deciduous woodland
2, 1, #Coniferous woodland
3, 0, #Arable
4, 0, #Improved grassland
5, 0, #Neutral grassland
6, 0, #Calcareous grassland
7, 0, #Acid grassland
8, 0, #Fen
9, 0, #Heather
10, 0, #Heather grassland
11, 0, #Bog
12, 0, #Inland rock
13, 0, #Saltwater
14, 0, #Freshwater
15, 0, #Supralittoral rock
16, 0, #Supralittoral sediment
```

```

17, 0, #Littoral rock
18, 0, #Littoral sediment
19, 0, #Saltmarsh
20, 0, #Urban
21, 0 #Suburban
), ncol = 2, byrow = TRUE) # these parameters format the matrix properly

# 9. create a hazard raster: (scale)(resolution)_(range)_haz_(season), and plot it
{scale}{resolution}_(range)_haz_{season} <- classify({scale}{resolution}_fuel,
{scale}{resolution}_(range)_matrix_{season}, include.lowest = TRUE)
{scale}{resolution}_(range)_haz_{season}
plot({scale}{resolution}_(range)_haz_{season})

# 10. List the non-burnable and non-natural cell values: 12 Inland rock; 13 Saltwater; 14
Freshwater; 15 Supralittoral rock; 16 Supralittoral sediment; 17 Littoral rock; 18
Littoral sediment; 19 Saltmarsh
{scale}{resolution}_(range)_nb_{season}_cell_values <- c(12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19)

# 11. Assign value of 1 to the cells in the list
# this line of code means: if the fuel grid cells are in the list, make it 1, otherwise
make it NA
{scale}{resolution}_(range)_nb_{season} <- ifel({scale}{resolution}_fuel %in%
{scale}{resolution}_(range)_nb_{season}_cell_values, 1, NA)

# 12. compute wildfire exposure, creating a new raster of exposure values for
'{scale}{resolution}' scale/resolution, '{range}' range, '{season}' season, and '{tdist}'
transmission distance, masking out the non-burnable cells:
(scale)(resolution)_(range)_burn_(season)
{scale}{resolution}_(range)_burn_{season}_buff <-
fire_exp({scale}{resolution}_(range)_haz_{season}, tdist = "{tdist}", no_burn =
{scale}{resolution}_(range)_nb_{season})
plot({scale}{resolution}_(range)_burn_{season}_buff)

# 13. plot burnable landscape with fireexposuR defaults
fire_exp_map_cont({scale}{resolution}_(range)_burn_{season})

# 14. classifying exposure in a table for an area of interest
summary_table_task{task} <-
fire_exp_summary({scale}{resolution}_(range)_burn_{season}_buff, aoi = area_of_interest,
classify = "landscape")
# view the summary table
summary_table_task{task}

# 15. export the summary table as a .csv file
write.csv(summary_table_task{task},
"{season}/{scale}/{resolution}/{range}/{scale}{resolution}_(range)_burn_{season}_summary_
table.csv")

```

```

# 16. remove the 600m buffer from the raster using the aoi polygon
# crop the raster back to the bounding box of the aoi
raster_cropped <- crop({scale}{resolution}_{range}_burn_{season}_buff, area_of_interest)

# mask the cropped raster to the exact shape of the aoi
{scale}{resolution}_{range}_burn_{season} <- mask(raster_cropped, area_of_interest)

# 17. export the clipped exposure raster as .tif file for use in ArcGIS
writeRaster({scale}{resolution}_{range}_burn_{season},
"{season}/{scale}/{resolution}/{range}/{scale}{resolution}_{range}_burn_{season}_task{tas
k}.tif")

```

I.2 WEA mail merge instructions – spring

```

# R script template 1 mail merge gluing
# Task {{Task}}, Scale {{Scale}}; Season {{Season}}, Resolution {{Resolution}}, Range
{{Range}}

# set my working directory
setwd("C:/Users/sarah/Documents/R Projects/2025")

# Load required packages
library(glue)
library(readr)

# Read the template as a single string
template <- read_file("R_Script_Template_1_spring.txt")

# Read the data (first row is header, next 11 rows are for Task_1 to Task_11)
mail_merge_data <- read_csv("Data_for_spring.csv")

# Loop over each row to create and save scripts named R_Script_Task_1.R to
R_Script_Task_11.R
for (i in seq_len(nrow(mail_merge_data))) {
  row <- as.list(mail_merge_data[i, ]) # Extract row as list for glue
  script_text <- glue(template, .envir = as.environment(row)) # Fill placeholders
  output_filename <- paste0("R_Script_Task_", i, ".R") # Fixed naming: Task_1 to Task_11
  write_file(script_text, output_filename) # Save the script
}

```

I.3 Example of WEA – task 1

```

# R script template 1 exposure
# Task no. 1, Scale Eng; Season sp, Resolution 10m, Range LExp, Transmission distance 1

```

```

# 1. check R, R Studio and fireexposuR are all up-to-date
# 2. check I have devtools
# 3. set my working directory
setwd("C:/Users/sarah/Documents/R Projects/2025")

# 4. load required libraries
library(fireexposuR)
library(terra)

# 5. read raster data to create: (scale)(resolution)_fuel
Eng10_fuel <- rast("Eng/10/Eng_10m.tif")

# 6. read vector data
area_of_interest <- vect("Eng/Eng_aoi.shp")

# 7. plot to see them
plot(Eng10_fuel)
plot(area_of_interest)

# 8. create a hazard reclassification matrix for the season:
(scale)(resolution)_(range)_matrix_(season)
# Ensure the binary classifications are for spring.
Eng10_LExp_matrix_sp <- matrix(c(1, 0, #Deciduous woodland
                                2, 1, #Coniferous woodland
                                3, 0, #Arable
                                4, 0, #Improved grassland
                                5, 0, #Neutral grassland
                                6, 0, #Calcareous grassland
                                7, 0, #Acid grassland
                                8, 0, #Fen
                                9, 0, #Heather
                                10, 0, #Heather grassland
                                11, 0, #Bog
                                12, 0, #Inland rock
                                13, 0, #Saltwater
                                14, 0, #Freshwater
                                15, 0, #Supralittoral rock
                                16, 0, #Supralittoral sediment
                                17, 0, #Littoral rock
                                18, 0, #Littoral sediment
                                19, 0, #Saltmarsh
                                20, 0, #Urban
                                21, 0 #Suburban
                                ), ncol = 2, byrow = TRUE) # these parameters format the matrix properly

# 9. create a hazard raster: (scale)(resolution)_(range)_haz_(season), and plot it

```

```

Eng10_LExp_haz_sp <- classify(Eng10_fuel, Eng10_LExp_matrix_sp, include.lowest = TRUE)
Eng10_LExp_haz_sp
plot(Eng10_LExp_haz_sp)

# 10. List the non-burnable and non-natural cell values: 12 Inland rock; 13 Saltwater; 14
Freshwater; 15 Supralittoral rock; 16 Supralittoral sediment; 17 Littoral rock; 18
Littoral sediment; 19 Saltmarsh
Eng10_LExp_nb_sp_cell_values <- c(12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19)

# 11. Assign value of 1 to the cells in the list
# this line of code means: if the fuel grid cells are in the list, make it 1, otherwise
make it NA
Eng10_LExp_nb_sp <- ifel(Eng10_fuel %in% Eng10_LExp_nb_sp_cell_values, 1, NA)

# 12. compute wildfire exposure, creating a new raster of exposure values for 'Eng10'
scale/resolution, 'LExp' range, 'sp' season, and '1' transmission distance, masking out
the non-burnable cells: (scale)(resolution)_(range)_burn_(season)
Eng10_LExp_burn_sp_buff <- fire_exp(Eng10_LExp_haz_sp, tdist = "1", no_burn =
Eng10_LExp_nb_sp)
plot(Eng10_LExp_burn_sp_buff)

# 13. plot burnable landscape with fireexposuR defaults
fire_exp_map_cont(Eng10_LExp_burn_sp_buff)

# 14. classifying exposure in a table for an area of interest
summary_table_task1 <- fire_exp_summary(Eng10_LExp_burn_sp_buff, aoi = area_of_interest,
classify = "landscape")
# view the summary table
summary_table_task1

# 15. export the summary table as a .csv file
write.csv(summary_table_task1, "sp/Eng/10/LExp/Eng10_LExp_burn_sp_summary_table.csv")

# 16. remove the 600m buffer from the raster using the aoi polygon
# crop the raster back to the bounding box of the aoi
raster_cropped <- crop(Eng10_LExp_burn_sp_buff, area_of_interest)

# mask the cropped raster to the exact shape of the aoi
Eng10_LExp_burn_sp <- mask(raster_cropped, area_of_interest)

# 17. export the clipped exposure raster as .tif file for use in ArcGIS
writeRaster(Eng10_LExp_burn_sp, "sp/Eng/10/LExp/Eng10_LExp_burn_sp_task1.tif")

```

I.4 WEA validation – long-range exposure

```
# R script wildfire exposure validation
```

```

# set my working directory
setwd("C:/Users/sarah/Documents/R Projects/2025")
# load required libraries
library(fireexposuR)
library(terra)
library(ggplot2)

burn_polygons <- vect("Burn_Data/Eng_burn_polygons.shp")

# 1. Long-range Exposure
LExp_raster <- rast("su/Eng/30/LExp/Eng30_LExp_burn_su_task13.tif")

# validation
LExp_validation_result <- fire_exp_validate(
  LExp_raster,
  burn_polygons
)

print(LExp_validation_result)

# view diagnostic plot:
fire_exp_validate_plot(LExp_validation_result)

ggsave("Burn_Data/LExp_val_result_500m_graph.png", width = 8, height = 6)

write.csv(LExp_validation_result, "Burn_Data/LExp_val_result_500m.csv", row.names =
FALSE)

```

I.5 Chi-squared test – long–range exposure

```

# Chi-squared test

# 1. set my working directory
setwd("C:/Users/sarah/Documents/R Projects/2025")

# 2. Read in the validation results
df <- read.csv("Burn_Data/LExp_val_result_500m.csv")

# 3. Filter for observed and expected groups
observed_df <- df[df$group == "Observed", ]
expected_df <- df[df$group == "Expected", ]

# 4. Match categories present in both observed and expected
common_bins <- intersect(observed_df$exp_vals, expected_df$exp_vals)
observed_df <- observed_df[observed_df$exp_vals %in% common_bins, ]

```

```

expected_df <- expected_df[expected_df$exp_vals %in% common_bins, ]

# 5. Create observed and expected vectors
observed_counts <- observed_df$n
expected_total <- sum(expected_df$n)
expected_props <- expected_df$n / expected_total
expected_counts <- expected_props * sum(observed_counts)

# 6. Run chi-squared test
chisq.test(x = observed_counts, p = expected_props, rescale.p = TRUE)

```

I.6 Wilcoxon rank sum test

```

# Wilcoxon rank sum test to compare distributions of exposure values between burned and
# unburned area to assess whether burned areas have significantly higher exposure values
# than unburned areas

# set my working directory
setwd("C:/Users/sarah/Documents/R Projects/2025")
# load required libraries
library(fireexposuR)
library(terra)

burn_polygons <- vect("Burn_Data/Eng_burn_polygons.shp")

# Long-range Exposure 500m, sample size 2%
LExp_raster <- rast("su/Eng/30/LExp/Eng30_LExp_burn_su_task13.tif")

# 1. Identify burned and unburned cells
burned_mask <- mask(LExp_raster, burn_polygons) # exposure values inside
burned areas
unburned_mask <- mask(LExp_raster, burn_polygons, inverse = TRUE) # exposure values
outside burned areas

# 2. Convert rasters to data frames and drop NAs
burned_values_df <- as.data.frame(burned_mask, xy = FALSE, na.rm = TRUE)
unburned_values_df <- as.data.frame(unburned_mask, xy = FALSE, na.rm = TRUE)

# 3. Randomly sample 2% from each group
set.seed(42) # for reproducibility
burned_sample <- burned_values_df[sample(nrow(burned_values_df), floor(0.02 *
nrow(burned_values_df))), , drop = FALSE]
unburned_sample <- unburned_values_df[sample(nrow(unburned_values_df), floor(0.02 *
nrow(unburned_values_df))), , drop = FALSE]

# 4. Rename columns to "value"

```

```

colnames(burned_sample) <- "value"
colnames(unburned_sample) <- "value"

# 5. Run Wilcoxon rank sum test
wilcox.test(burned_sample$value, unburned_sample$value)

```

I.7 DVA validation

```

# DVA validation
# calculate % of each dissolved polyline in high-exposure zones

# 1. set the working directory
setwd("C:/Users/sarah/Documents/R Projects/2025")

# 2. Load required packages
library(terra)      # for spatial operations
library(dplyr)      # for data manipulation
library(ggplot2)    # for histogram

# 3. Set threshold
thresh_exp <- 0.8

# 4. Read raster and dissolved polylines
exposure <- rast("su/Eng/30/SExp/Eng30_SExp_burn_su_task23.tif")
lines <- vect("C:/Users/sarah/Documents/ArcGIS/Projects/Burn Data/Burn Data.gdb",
             layer = "Eng_polylines_dissolved")

# 5. Define join field - Confirm that arcid still exists after dissolving
join_att <- "arcid"

# 6. Reclassify raster to binary: 1 = high exposure, NA = not high
rmat <- matrix(c(0, thresh_exp, NA,
                thresh_exp, 1, 1), ncol = 3, byrow = TRUE)
highexposure <- classify(exposure, rmat, include.lowest = TRUE)

# 7. Convert binary raster to polygons
highexppoly <- as.polygons(highexposure)

# 8. Calculate original line lengths
lines$original_length <- perim(lines)

# 9. Intersect lines with high exposure polygons
inters <- terra::intersect(lines, highexppoly)

# 10. Calculate intersected lengths
inters$inters_length <- perim(inters)

```

```

# 11. Summarise total intersected length per arcid
inters_summary <- as.data.frame(inters) %>%
  group_by(arcid) %>%
  summarise(inters_length = sum(inters_length, na.rm = TRUE))

# 12. Merge back with original lines
lines_prop_intersect <- terra::merge(lines, inters_summary, by = "arcid", all = TRUE)
lines_prop_intersect$inters_length <- ifelse(is.na(lines_prop_intersect$inters_length),
0, lines_prop_intersect$inters_length)
lines_prop_intersect$prop_intersection <- lines_prop_intersect$inters_length /
lines_prop_intersect$original_length

# 13. Create summary table
line_exposure_summary <- lines_prop_intersect |>
  as.data.frame() |>
  select(ID = arcid, prop_intersection)

# 14. Plot histogram (limit x-axis to 200%)
ggplot(line_exposure_summary, aes(x = prop_intersection * 100)) +
  geom_histogram(binwidth = 5, colour = "black", fill = "lightblue") +
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 200)) +
  labs(
    title = "Distribution of High Exposure Percentage per Line",
    x = "% of line in high-exposure area",
    y = "Number of lines"
  )

# 15. Save plot
ggsave("Burn_Data/Eng30_SExp_highexp_polyline_graph.png", width = 8, height = 5, dpi =
300)

# 16. Summary statistics
mean_percent <- mean(line_exposure_summary$prop_intersection * 100, na.rm = TRUE)
median_percent <- median(line_exposure_summary$prop_intersection * 100, na.rm = TRUE)

# 17. Export summary table
write.csv(line_exposure_summary,
  "Burn_Data/Eng30_SExp_highexp_polyline_summary.csv",
  row.names = FALSE)

# 18. optional - shorten the x axis on the graph
ggplot(line_exposure_summary, aes(x = prop_intersection * 100)) +
  geom_histogram(binwidth = 5, colour = "black", fill = "lightblue") +
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 100)) +
  labs(
    title = "Distribution of High Exposure Percentage per Line",

```

```

    x = "% of line in high-exposure area",
    y = "Number of lines"
)

```

I.8 DVA template – default 5–km segment length

```

# R script template 6 directional vulnerability polygon
# Task no. {dvtask}, Scale {scale}; Season {season}, Resolution {resolution}m, Range
{range}, Transmission distance {tdist}, polygon {poly}

# 1. check R, R Studio and fireexposuR are all up-to-date
# 2. check I have devtools
# 3. set my working directory
setwd("C:/Users/sarah/Documents/R Projects/2025")

# 4. load required libraries
library(fireexposuR)
library(terra)

# 5. Read raster exposure data with terra
{scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season} <-
rast("{season}/{scale}/{resolution}/{range}/{scale}{resolution}_{range}_burn_{season}_tas
k{task}.tif")

# 6. Read polygon feature with terra
{poly}_poly <- vect("Polygons/{poly}_poly.shp")

# 7. make sure the crs match exactly by projecting the polygon to match exposure
{poly}_poly <- project({poly}_poly, crs({scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}))

# 8. Assess directional vulnerability
# directional vulnerability transects to a polygon
{scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly} <- fire_exp_dir(
  {scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season},
  {poly}_poly,
  thresh_exp = 0.8,
  thresh_viable = 1.0
)

# 9. explore the objects we just created
# terra object summary
{scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly}

# 10. look at the attribute table
# head() shows the first 6 rows
head({scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly})

```

```

# 11. Visualize directional vulnerability transects (radial plot)
# map directional vulnerability to polygon
fire_exp_dir_plot({scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly})

# 12. in a map
fire_exp_dir_map({scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly})

# 13. for mapping, adding the aoi polygon in again will add it to the map in black
fire_exp_dir_map({scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly}, {poly}_poly)

# 14. export your transects as a shapefile
writeVector({scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly},
"Radials/{scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly}.shp")

```

I.9 DVA template – 1-km segment length

```

# R script template 6 directional vulnerability polygon
# Task no. {dvatask}, Scale {scale}; Season {season}, Resolution {resolution}m, Range
{range}, Transmission distance {tdist}, polygon {poly}

# 1. check R, R Studio and fireexposuR are all up-to-date
# 2. check I have devtools
# 3. set my working directory
setwd("C:/Users/sarah/Documents/R Projects/2025")

# 4. load required libraries
library(fireexposuR)
library(terra)

# 5. Read raster exposure data with terra
{scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season} <-
rast("{season}/{scale}/{resolution}/{range}/{scale}{resolution}_{range}_burn_{season}_tas
k{task}.tif")

# 6. Read polygon feature with terra
{poly}_poly <- vect("Polygons/{poly}_poly.shp")

# 7. make sure the crs match exactly by projecting the polygon to match exposure
{poly}_poly <- project({poly}_poly, crs({scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}))

# 8. Assess directional vulnerability
# directional vulnerability transects to a polygon
{scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly} <- fire_exp_dir(
  {scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season},
  {poly}_poly,
  t_lengths = c(1000, 1000, 1000), # three 1-km segments

```

```

    thresh_exp = 0.8,
    thresh_viable = 1.0
)

# 9. explore the objects we just created
# terra object summary
{scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly}

# 10. look at the attribute table
# head() shows the first 6 rows
head({scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly})

# 11. Visualize directional vulnerability transects (radial plot)
# map directional vulnerability to polygon
fire_exp_dir_plot({scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly})

# 12. in a map
fire_exp_dir_map({scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly})

# 13. for mapping, adding the aoI polygon in again will add it to the map in black
fire_exp_dir_map({scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly}, {poly}_poly)

# 14. export your transects as a shapefile
writeVector({scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly},
"Radials/{scale}{resolution}_{range}_{season}_dva_{poly}_1km.shp")

```

I.10 DVA mail merge instructions

```

# R script template 7 mail merge gluing
# DVATask {{dvatask}}, Task {{task}}, Scale {{scale}}; Season {{season}}, Resolution
{{resolution}}, Range {{range}}, Poly {{poly}}

# Load required packages
library(glue)
library(readr)

# Read the template as a single string
template <- read_file("R_Script_Template_6_dva_poly.txt")

# Read the data (first row is header, next 27 rows are for dvatask_30 to dvatask_56)
mail_merge_data <- read_csv("Data_for_dva.csv")

# Loop over each row to create and save scripts named R_Script_Task_30.R to
R_Script_Task_56.R
for (i in seq_len(nrow(mail_merge_data))) {
  row <- as.list(mail_merge_data[i, ]) # Extract row as list for glue

```

```

script_text <- glue(template, .envir = as.environment(row)) # Fill placeholders
output_filename <- paste0("R_Script_Task_", i + 29, ".R") # Fixed naming: Task_30 to
Task_56
write_file(script_text, output_filename) # Save the script
}

```

I.11 Example of DVA – task 30

```

# R script template 6 directional vulnerability polygon
# Task no. 30, Scale DH; Season su, Resolution 10m, Range SExp, Transmission distance s,
polygon BBS

# 1. check R, R Studio and fireexposuR are all up-to-date
# 2. check I have devtools
# 3. set my working directory
setwd("C:/Users/sarah/Documents/R Projects/2025")

# 4. load required libraries
library(fireexposuR)
library(terra)

# 5. Read raster exposure data with terra
DH10_SExp_su <- rast("su/DH/10/SExp/DH10_SExp_burn_su_task17.tif")

# 6. Read polygon feature with terra
BBS_poly <- vect("Polygons/BBS_poly.shp")

# 7. make sure the crs match exactly by projecting the polygon to match exposure
BBS_poly <- project(BBS_poly, crs(DH10_SExp_su))

# 8. Assess directional vulnerability
# directional vulnerability transects to a polygon
DH10_SExp_su_dva_BBS <- fire_exp_dir(
  DH10_SExp_su,
  BBS_poly,
  thresh_exp = 0.8,
  thresh_viable = 1.0
)

# 9. explore the objects we just created
# terra object summary
DH10_SExp_su_dva_BBS

# 10. look at the attribute table
# head() shows the first 6 rows
head(DH10_SExp_su_dva_BBS)

```

```
# 11. Visualize directional vulnerability transects (radial plot)
# map directional vulnerability to polygon
fire_exp_dir_plot(DH10_SExp_su_dva_BBS)

# 12. in a map
fire_exp_dir_map(DH10_SExp_su_dva_BBS)

# 13. for mapping, adding the aoI polygon in again will add it to the map in black
fire_exp_dir_map(DH10_SExp_su_dva_BBS, BBS_poly)

# 14. export your transects as a shapefile
writeVector(DH10_SExp_su_dva_BBS, "Radials/DH10_SExp_su_dva_BBS.shp")
```

Appendix J. WEA script parameter combinations and task numbers

A combination of parameters was used to generate the 23 WEA scripts, using the glue package in R as a mail merge function.

Table J1. Parameter combinations used to generate the 23 wildfire exposure assessment scripts.

Land–cover raster resolutions in blue, seasons in purple, transmission distances in orange, and the resulting task numbers in red. Pink cells indicate that the resolution was too coarse for the transmission distance (Appendix G.2, point 5). Grey cells indicate assessments not included in the study.

England				
spring	10m	30m	50m	100m
long (500m)	1	2	3	4
summer	10m	30m	50m	100m
long (500m)	11	12	13	14
long (300m)		21		
long (200m)		22		
short (100m)		23		

Dorset–Hampshire				
spring	10m	30m	50m	100m
long (500m)	5	7	9	10
short (100m)	6	8		
summer	10m	30m	50m	100m
long (500m)	15	17	19	20
short (100m)	16	18		

Appendix K. Long-range exposure validation for 300 m and 200 m transmission distances

The comparison between expected (dashed bar) and observed (solid bar) burned area proportion for long-range exposure at 300 m and 200 m transmission distances (Figure K1) revealed a surplus of burned cells in the Nil exposure class, indicating that fires burned preferentially in low exposure areas. The long-range WEA is not validated at the 300 m or 200 m transmission distances.

Plot generated with fireexposuR()

Figure continues on next page

Figure K1 (continued)

(b) 200 m transmission distance

Figure K1. Comparison between expected and observed burned area across exposure class for 300 m and 200 m transmission distances.

Comparison between expected (dashed bar) and observed (solid bar) burned area across exposure class (summer hazard classification) using a 0.5% sample (left) and total (right): (a) 300 m transmission distance and (b) 200 m transmission distance.

Appendix L. Statistical test results for long-range and short-range exposure

Table L1. Statistical test results for long-range and short-range exposure (summer hazard classification).

	Chi-squared test	Wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction
Long-range (500 m)	$\chi^2 = 155083$ $df = 11$ $p = < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$	$W = 2.7838 \times 10^{10}$ $p = < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$
Short-range (100 m)	$\chi^2 = 1132186$ $df = 11$ $p = < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$	$W = 5.3871 \times 10^{10}$ $p = < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$

Appendix M. DVA radial graph outputs for all values and segment lengths

M.1 DVA radial graphs with 5-km segment length

(a) BBS

(b) BranThorn

Figure M1. Directional vulnerability assessment radial graphs with 5-km segment length.

Directional vulnerability assessment radial graphs with 5-km segment length for (a) BBS and (b) BranThorn.

M.2 DVA radial graphs with 3-km segment length

(a) BBS

(b) Beaulieu

Figure continues on next page

Figure M2 (continued)

(c) BranThorn

(d) Brockenhurst

(e) East Boldre

(f) Lyndhurst

Figure continues on next page

Figure M2 (continued)

(g) Ringwood *et al.*

(h) Sandy Down

(i) Sway

(j) BCP *et al.*

Figure M2. Directional vulnerability assessment radial graphs with 3-km segment length.

Directional vulnerability assessment radial graphs with 3-km segment length for (a) BBS, (b) Beaulieu, (c) BranThorn, (d) Brockenhurst, (e) East Boldre, (f) Lyndhurst, (g) Ringwood *et al.*, (h) Sandy Down, (i) Sway, and (j) BCP *et al.*

M.3 DVA radial graphs with 1-km segment length

(a) BBS

(b) Beaulieu

(c) BranThorn

(d) Brockenhurst

Figure continues on next page

Figure M3 (continued)

(e) East Boldre

(f) Lymington *et al.*

(g) Lyndhurst

(h) Ringwood *et al.*

Figure continues on next page

Figure M3 (continued)

(i) Sandy Down

(j) Sway

(k) Tiptoe *et al.*

(l) BCP *et al.*

Figure continues on next page

Figure M3 (continued)

(m) Wareham

(n) Dorchester

(o) PI conifer plantation

(p) FCS conservation area

Figure M3. Directional vulnerability assessment radial graphs with 1-km segment length.

Directional vulnerability assessment radial graphs with 1-km segment length for (a) BBS, (b) Beaulieu, (c) BranThorn, (d) Brockenhurst, (e) East Boldre, (f) Lymington *et al.*, (g) Lyndhurst, (h) Ringwood *et al.*, (i) Sandy Down, (j) Sway and (k) Tiptoe *et al.*, (l) BCP *et al.*, (m) Wareham, (n) Dorchester, (o) PI conifer plantation, and (p) FCS conservation area.